

**The Voice of the Voiceless: The Subversion of
Gender Roles in Madeline Miller's *Circe* and
Jennifer Saint's *Ariadne*.**

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**THE VOICE OF THE VOICELESS: THE SUBVERSION OF GENDER ROLES
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THESIS APPROVAL PAGE

I certify that in my opinion the thesis submitted by Manar RAYYAN titled “THE VOICE OF THE VOICELESS: THE SUBVERSION OF GERNDER ROLES IN MADELINE MILLER’S CIRCE AND JENNIFER SAINT’S ARIADNE” is fully adequate in scope and in quality as a thesis for the degree of Master of Science.

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this thesis is the result of my own work and all information included has been obtained and expounded in accordance with the academic rules and ethical policy specified by the institute. Besides, I declare that all the statements, results, materials, not original to this thesis have been cited and referenced literally.

Without being bound by a particular time, I accept all moral and legal consequences of any detection contrary to the aforementioned statement.

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FOREWORD

I would like to appreciate and express my sincere gratitude to my supervisor Assoc.Prof.Dr. Harith Ismael Turki who helped me complete my Masters. His guidance and directions enabled me to successfully complete every phase of writing my thesis. I also want to express my gratitude to my dear mother and family for their support and tolerance as I worked on my research and drafted my thesis. I have made it thus far thanks to your support for me. Without your assistance, I could not have finished this work.

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ABSTRACT

The interdisciplinary discipline of gender studies investigates the intricate relationships between gender and other identification indicators like race, ethnicity, sexual orientation, class, and nationality. It assesses the ways in which gender affects individual experiences, social structures, and cultural expressions. The study of men's roles and identities, the experiences of women as the second gender, and the larger idea of gender as a social construct are just a few of the issues covered by this area, which has expanded throughout the years. This thesis is an endeavour to navigate the foundation and concepts of gender within the societal and sex binary context by exploring the history of the field's evolution and its interconnections to race, nation, biological sex, the social structure, and gender norms, as well by analysing both Madeline Miller and Jennifer Saint's mythological novels *Circe* and *Ariadne* in order to explore the gender system and the significance of defying gender on the grounds of the theories of Simone de Beauvoir and Judith Butler. The study concludes that both authors utilized the gender system to highlight and challenge the social norms that women are expected to conform to. In this framework, both works did a perfect job of portraying the oppressive systems that their protagonists continuously struggle to overcome. By doing this, they were able to effectively give their characters a voice and an identity of their own, breaking the associations they had with the societal structure and gender roles they were a part of.

Keywords: Gender; Gender/ Sex System; Gender Roles; *Circe*; *Ariadne*; Greek Mythology.

ÖZ

Cinsiyet çalışmalarının disiplinler arası yönü, cinsiyet ile ırk, etnik köken, cinsel yönelim, sınıf ve milliyet gibi diğer kimlik göstergeleri arasındaki karmaşık ilişkileri araştırır. İnsanların deneyimlerinin, toplumsal kurumların ve kültürel ifadelerin cinsiyetten nasıl etkilendiğini değerlendirir. Erkeklerin rolleri ve kimliklerinin incelenmesi, ikinci cinsiyet olarak kadınların deneyimleri ve toplumsal bir yapı olarak toplumsal cinsiyet fikri, yıllar içinde genişleyen bu alanın kapsadığı konulardan sadece birkaçıdır. Bu tez, toplumsal ve cinsiyet ikiliği bağlamında cinsiyetin temellerini ve kavramlarını keşfetmeye yönelik bir çabadır. Cinsiyet çalışmalarının tarihini ve ırk, ulus, biyolojik cinsiyet, toplumsal yapı ve cinsiyet normlarıyla olan ilişkilerini inceleyerek, Madeline Miller'ın 'Circe' ve Jennifer Saint'in 'Ariadne' mitolojik romanlarını analiz eder. Bu romanlar aracılığıyla cinsiyet sistemini, rolleri ve cinsiyetin sınırlarına meydan okumanın önemini, Simone de Beauvoir ve Judith Butler'ın teorileri temelinde araştırır. Çalışma, her iki yazarın da toplumsal normlara dikkat çekmek ve bu normlara meydan okumak için cinsiyet sistemini kullandığını ortaya koyar. Bu bağlamda, kahramanlarının sürekli olarak mücadele ettiği baskıcı sistemleri mükemmel bir şekilde tasvir etmişlerdir. Bu sayede, yazarlar karakterlerine kendi seslerini ve kimliklerini etkili bir şekilde kazandırmış, onların içinde buldukları toplumsal yapıyla olan bağlarını koparmışlardır.

Anahtar Kelimeler : Cinsiyet; Cinsiyet Sistemi; Cinsiyet Roller; Circe; Ariadne; Yunan Mitolojisi

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SUBJECT OF THE RESEARCH

Due to the importance of the subject of subverting gender norms and the suffering and difficulties that women go through as a result of conventional society standards. This study aims to investigate how gender preconceptions are subverted by *Circe* and *Ariadne's* retellings of Greek mythology. The primary goal of the research is to examine and elucidate the various methods employed by the authors to offer a fresh feminist interpretation of those myths and their endeavours to challenge the prevalent pattern of narratives that are predominantly male-oriented.

PURPOSE AND IMPORTANCE OF THE RESEARCH

The purpose of this study is to examine how *Circe* and *Ariadne*' retellings of Greek mythology subvert gender stereotypes. Consequently, the study's objective is to explain and scrutinize the different techniques that the writers used to present a new feminist perspective on those myths and their attempts to defy the trend of traditionally male-dominated narratives

METHOD OF THE RESEARCH

The analysis will be completed utilising a qualitative research methodology that entails carefully reading the text and analysing it in the context of gender studies and feminism theory. The concepts of subverting gender roles and patriarchy in the novels, as well as the depiction of disenfranchised female characters, will be examined by the researcher using a combination of content analysis and discourse analysis. A thorough analysis of the postmodern feminism and the subversion of gender roles theories, as well as its applicability to the studied novels, will also be done by the researcher. Reviewing academic papers, books, and other pertinent materials that provide insight on the thesis's theoretical underpinnings will be required to do this.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE RESEARCH / RESEARCH PROBLEM

The research aims to discuss different issues surrounding the Subversion of Gender roles:

1. What impact does a female perspective have on a narrative that is traditionally presented from a male viewpoint?
2. How does society view female protagonists, their struggle and roles within the novels' contexts?
3. How does their voice impact their perspectives in their environments?
4. What are the factors and causes that lead to these characters' development?
5. Do patriarchy, traditional Greek stereotypes of women and marginalizing these characters have a role in shaping their identities, viewpoints and the narratives within the context of the retellings?

INTRODUCTION

Notwithstanding the constraints and ambiguities of Feminism, the term nevertheless denotes an ideology of liberation for women. The discourse of the emancipatory politics behind it is the current circumstances that women live in are oppressive and need to be altered. Feminism assumes the ambitions of taking actions to transform such realities that were imposed upon them. Nonetheless, the definition of Feminism itself, despite the general beliefs, has never been historically defined or stable (Delmar 1986); the object of this movement itself was altered due to many factors and circumstantial elements, hence, it can be said that the movement assumed many other ideologies and politics that included different minorities and genders throughout history; such discourses came to be as a result to the emergence of other gender identities or shifts that also vary depending on the cultural norms and opportunities (Butler 1990).

Regardless of such shifts, the presuppositions of feminism stay stable in terms of the main discourse. Feminism primarily assumes effective tactics for achieving change by making sense of the circumstances faced by women and other minorities. Feminist philosopher Marilyn Frye (1983) argues that oppression of women or members of oppressed groups can be understood as limitations on their alternatives in life as a result of their identity. In this instance, exploitation, reprimanding, powerlessness, cultural imperialism, and violence can all be considered forms of oppression (Young, 1990). The result of these persecutions is what is known as "epistemic injustice" (Fricker, 2007). In these cases, oppression causes a complete change in the way that an individual views the world and, as a result, their knowledge and credibility are regarded as lacking because they belong to or identify as a member of a marginalised group. Therefore, it is feasible to consider this movement as an epistemic justice movement, with the underlying assumptions being that the world will be changed by recognising and preserving the viewpoints of people who have experienced and lived their lives as 'women'. The importance of their experiences would eventually be acknowledged as a consequence of such conduct, which would likewise alter the systemic unfairness that is aimed at them in terms of social, cultural, and educational tolerance.

It is essential to take into account that across history, the struggles of women towards their marginalised class have reached new heights. In the 1970s, for illustration, these difficulties were brought about by a number of issues, including equal rights,

violence, heterosexual relationships, and the societal frameworks surrounding women. However, these periods were not particularly unique in the sense that women's movements did not cause a spark or a change at the time. Nevertheless, throughout history's early modern periods, women have been involved in numerous global movements in conjunction with nationalist and anti-colonialist justice movements, among others.

All things considered, these served to advance an alternative viewpoint for women, irrespective of their economic, political, or social class; as a result, these instances have as well influenced the movement's identity and, by extension, its history. Feminism, hence, played multiple roles throughout history in forming many liberation movements and thus helping other subordinate groups reclaim their rights. Additionally, it is worth noting that feminism, as a widespread movement, perceived women's circumstances not only on a social or an outer level, but also raised a question at the initial classifications of sex and gender. In order to expand on the original discourse, numerous sub theories were developed on larger scale utilising various variables, including sex, gender, race, ethnicity and class. Consequently, in the first chapter of this thesis, the theoretical foundation of gender studies is covered, along with the history of the field's evolution and its interconnections to race, nation, biological sex, the social structure, and gender norms.

Moreover, Homer portrays Circe, the golden-eyed goddess, as a wicked witch, banished in the island of Aea, who relishes transforming men into pigs in the *Odyssey* as well as a goddess who seethes in jealousy towards the wife of Odysseus. Nevertheless, her character, just like many female mythical characters, was meant to serve as a device for the development of Odysseus as the hero of his epic. Madeline Miller's novel *Circe* weaved together the origins of these myths and recreated the story of Circe using a feminist narrative in her contemporary version of the well-known classic tale, while also paying homage to Homer's epic.

The author does not only illuminate Circe in a new light, but also, she examines her characteristics as a woman who had an opportunity to access power. Miller's novel thoroughly revises Circe's struggle from early livelihood and utilises the mythological settings to develop her character in an ingenious way. *Circe* was published in 2018, following her acclaimed retelling of the tale of Achilles, that illuminates the queer

relationship between Patroclus and Achilles in the context of *The Iliad*. *Circe*, similarly, to *The Song of Achilles*, managed to be the top Bestseller following its publication. The novel also received the 2019 Women's Prize for Fiction shortlist, in addition to the Indies Choice Best Adult Fiction of the Year and Best Audiobook of the Year awards. On top of that, *Circe* received the 2018 Elle Big Book Award, The Red Tentacle Award, and an American Library Association Alex Award.

Miller's retelling does not only embody the original mythology, but it also depicts many womanly struggles that were imposed on the female characters. It is important to note that Greek mythology had the tendency to illuminate women's roles in society in an extreme yet familiar way to how women are often treated in realistic social settings. In this sense, *Circe* sheds the light on a lot of issues regarding the social structure, the objectifying of women, sexual harassment, male dominance, and the patriarchal elements of the family, as well the social and the female and male relationship systems.

Miller noted in one of her interviews that she intended to showcase and embody the male anxiety that comes when female characters are able to acquire power (Alter, 2018). Furthermore, Miller's depiction does not go astray from the original myth. Instead, she makes sure to weave her recreation together with what Homer offered, by using the attributes Circe's character was described with as a tool for her to elaborate on her story. For instance, in Annalisa Quinn's review on the novel, she elaborates on how the author used Circe's original descriptions such as her 'human voice' and 'braided hair' to build relationships and her strength instead of having them being traits of her weakness and insignificance (2018). Miller's utilisation of these traits helps the reader understand the development of the character, rather than dismissing them as trivial traits unlike the original myth. Nevertheless, it is critical to recognise that *Circe* is not only a retelling of her story but also the emergence of a voice for women and female characters who were previously viewed as little more than props and instruments for male heroes. It is easy to connect Miller's portrayal of Circe and the use of her perspective with Audre Lorde's emphasis on the value of poetics—that is, how language gives a woman's experience a voice and, consequently, an acknowledgment of her struggles—by giving the character the ability to speak, to depict her life, and to highlight her struggles and hardships (1984).

In addition, the narrative delves into the difficulties faced by the witch as a female character and explores the boundaries of power and how transcending them might result in defying social standards related to gender. As such, it offers a fresh perspective on these women and their experiences. The concept that one 'becomes' a woman and can 'unbecome' one when given the option and access to power is reflected in Miller's writing. The possibilities and lengths that female characters can achieve when they learn to appreciate their bodies and transgress social norms without losing sight of their femininity and identities are reflected in *Circe's* narrative.

It can be stated that Miller's writing is an effective attempt to use literature as a vehicle for translating women's experiences. In addition, Miller's work examines traditional myths and stories that dehumanise, minimise, and treat women as tools for their male characters. However, it might be said that *Circe* addresses the challenges of women in both the modern day and the previous several centuries, even though it is a 21st-century modern retelling. The work can be interpreted as a critique of gender norms and the socially constructed framework that we have yet to abolish, as well as an allegory of women's struggles and a mirror of feminism. Nonetheless, the second chapter of this work explores the gender system in *Circe*, analysing gender norms and the significance of defying gender grounded in the theories of Simone de Beauvoir and Judith Butler.

Furthermore, Ariadne, the princess and daughter of King Minos of Crete, is portrayed in classical mythology in a variety of fashions. In her debut novel *Ariadne*, Jennifer Saint implemented the heroine's perspective, much to Madeline Miller's recourse to *Circe*, to produce a distinctive portrayal of gender and contemporary feminist theses. She embodies these portrayals while employing them to her advantage. The most well-known aspect of Ariadne's narrative is how she courageously aided Theseus in his battle with the Minotaur and then got abandoned by him on the island of Naxos. In order to analyse her character's growth and tragedy in tremendous detail, Saint offers a fresh interpretation of the myth, which she embodies without modifying. Her work deftly questions and examines Ariadne's actions and development while concurrently tracing the development of her sister Phaedra. The writer's integration of both of their points of view sheds light on the ways in which women battle the dominance of male figures, their own rage, the struggles associated with motherhood and womanhood, as well as the political battle within the social framework that places little value on a woman's existence. Using the lives of various women as a model, Saint's debut novel provides a

thorough examination of all these facets. In each case, Saint illustrates how the women were all doomed to the same fate because of their position in the social structure of their immediate environment.

Ariadne, Saint's debut novel was a finalist for the Goodreads Choice Awards in the fantasy/mythology category and was nominated for Waterstones Book of the Year 2021. The novel narrates the life of Ariadne as she matures into her social role, embracing her dancing and her childhood ambition of marrying a hero, having grown up hearing tales of gods and heroic epics. In the end, she defies the gods and everyone around her to ensure she conforms to her role. Nevertheless, Ariadne was a victim who was abandoned to preserve Theseus's valiant legacy, much like many other female mythological figures. In this respect, Saint capitalises on this mythology to address and provide answers for the various manners in which these ancient and classical myths present women as an expense that those men must pay for their lust, wrath, and greed. This is not to argue that male figures such as Theseus are flat and presented as one-dimensional antagonists. Saint enables the reader to comprehend these more extremely portrayed people by providing them with a nuanced character development. That being said, this neither justifies or normalises their actions (Bedford, 2021).

Saint also delves into the life of Phaedra, the younger princess and Ariadne's sister, highlighting her struggles and the ongoing marginalisation she faces due to her gender, as well as the ways in which she attempts to overcome these constraints. Both Ariadne and Phaedra are isolated from the outside world and shielded from its impacts in Crete. Because they lack the discernment to recognise that Theseus is manipulating them, they must deal with a betrayal in his character from the beginning. For Phaedra, Athens turns into a place where reality crumbles, a large metropolis full of odd people and odd customs. She experiences an enormous amount of transition there, and everything that goes wrong in the Athens palace directly affects her character (Kathryn, 2022). The novel thus offers a hypnotic yet utterly propulsive epic that weaves itself into the original myth and creates a voice to the women of Greek mythology as they were never given one. Saint's work, similarly to Miller's, attempts to transform every aspect of these female characters in order to demonstrate their roles and heroic features that are as equally valuable as the male heroes'. The retelling also highlights the characters' growth and attempts to deviate from their gender roles in search of their authentic selves. Therefore, chapter three, in accordance with the theory of gender, follows Butler's thesis

on gender acts, Beauvoir's examination of women's roles in *The Second Sex*, Rubin Gayle's dissertation on the gender/sex system, the patriarchal structure, and the hierarchical classism of women.

1. CHAPTER ONE: Theoretical Background

1.1. The Biological Notion of Gender

Regardless of the developments of the status of women as a marginalised group, many feminist scientists and socialists accumulated evidence to prove the ‘natural’ imbalance between the two sexes (Delphy,1993). Those claims however, did not go unchallenged throughout the years, which brings us back to the initial discourse of feminism and its perspective of women in terms of gender; for Simone de Beauvoir caused an uproar in the academic and scientific world with her conservative yet empowering piece on women’s gender and sex as the ‘Other’ or the ‘second sex’ (1953).

It is evident that many feminist pioneers found themselves challenging the systematic othering of women in its very roots before moving to the external problems. Beauvoir, as one of the founders of the gender theory, as well one of the most acclaimed founders of the new wave of feminism, was one of the first feminists to publish an exhaustive treatise on women’s conditions in that regard.

Beauvoir’s piece revolved around the basis of how the two sexes are classified. In her work, *The Second Sex*, she asserted that the relation of the two sexes is not like ‘two electrical poles’, for the sex of men can be seen as the representation of the “neutral” and “positive” sex, for the general usage of ‘man’ is perceived as the natural or the rightful way to refer to humans. On the other hand, the associations around the sex of ‘women’ are rather negative and not recognised as natural or acceptable. For as Beauvoir claimed, “a man is in the right in being a man; it is the woman who is in the wrong”. She thus declares that such language and social perspectives amount to the fact that there is only one truthful humankind, which can be referred to as the masculine, and those biological features of men can be seen as a natural and a direct association to being connected to the world as the ‘apprehensive sex’ as a matter of fact. This consequently leads to perceiving the body or the sex of women as the total contrast of such a positive view, regarding her body as a “hindrance”, “a prison” and “weighed down by everything peculiar to it” (1953). Due to such classifications, Beauvoir concluded that this is mainly what led society to regard men or the male body as the definition for humanity. Meaning that male is humanity and women or females do not amount to that.

Women are therefore viewed by men as a second gender that must be prescribed, or as a relative or creature that is far from being "self-sufficient." She is what people take her to be—literally, no more, no less. Meaning that, women cannot exist without men however that cannot be said for men. Women therefore are not as necessary to humanity the way men are, they are a subjective matter, up to a debate in regards of importance, however, as humanity cannot be perceived as 'being' without the default gender assigned to it, male, men are seen as absolute and cannot be othered; consequently, came women to be 'the other' (1953).

The notion made by many Anglophone feminists that women's fate is primarily determined by their biology was supported by Beauvoir's study. As a result, they expanded by developing a fresh gender discourse to theorise the beliefs pertaining to the sex-based disparities in systems. A notable demonstration in that regard would be the work of Ann Oakley's *Sex, Gender, and Society*, in which she criticised the empirical data on sex differences. She starts her argument by asserting that the data in itself is rather exaggerated by the scientific approaches to weigh them. The entire imbalance of such data was rooted in the way most of those scientific claims were mostly 'man-made' interpretations to reassure and secure men's position and dominance in society by degrading women's 'natural' bodies, sexual and biological differences.

As a case in point. sex differences were used in the 1970s to argue against women becoming airline pilots since they would not be able to execute their jobs as well as males due to their monthly hormonal fluctuations (Rogers, 1999). Or women's sizes and masculine abilities were compared to the male bodies and seen as inferior as a matter of fact; these instances amount to Oakley's assertion to how biological differences were used up until recently to marginalise women as the othered or the second gender. Oakley further, claimed that masculine and feminine roles were more rooted in social standards rather than scientific ones. She elaborates on this idea by asserting that these are products of society in order to internalise certain behaviours and traits that can be seen as acceptable depending on the sex. Which, consequently, led to the gap between both genders rather than it being due to 'scientific' or 'biological' differences. Oakley backed up her thesis by amassing evidence from a variety of cultures in regard to how women and men are perceived and further described the traits and the activities that were deemed as appropriate for both sex groups, proving further the social connections to these claimed facts by scientists.

The piece titled "The Traffic in Woman: Notes on the Political Economy of Sex" by Gayle Rubin is another noteworthy illustration centred around these gendered disparities. In the same way as Oakley. The cultural structure and its relationships to gender or the methodical procedures around it appeared to be further developed in Rubin's work.

Rubin believed that the sex/ gender system is initially organised by society in order to create or reproduce biological sexualities into commodities of human behaviours in order to satisfy the sexual needs of humanity. Rubin elaborates by claiming that this system is not as simple as it being a "mode of production" but also when are made to be coupled, these 'gendered' beings are meant to create families as a social product, hence the entire system positions women by constraining them to certain roles in society to be eventually exchanged as objects by men and do their 'role' of creating families and communities:

The formation of a gender identity is an example of production in the realm of the sexual system. And a sex/gender system involves more than the "relations of procreation," reproduction in the biological sense. ... At the most general level, the social organisation of sex rests upon gender, obligatory heterosexuality, and the constraint of female sexuality. (Gayle, 1975)

Followed by this assertion, Rubin cites the exchange or the trade of women in many cultures and patriarchal civilizations keeps the pattern of oppression of women alive. Likewise, many political feminists that specialise in multiracial and postcolonial fields elaborated on the same argument in terms of the impact of such classifications on other cultures. For Western theorists did not only divide women based on the bodily differences but also on the external racial features depending on the cultures, exotifying the sexuality of women in other civilisations and regarding them as almost inanimate objects and prizes for political challenges and western perspectives, naturally leading in distorting their heritage (Lorde. 1981). These conceptions mainly resulted in adding on the beliefs that men are universally dominant and naturally women are to be subjected under the exact patriarchal system due to their bodily differences, making them a marginalised group that are second to humanity, adding to Beauvoir's assertion of the second sex, and further her claim that "social discrimination produces in women moral and intellectual effects so profound that they appear to be caused by nature" (Beauvoir, 1972) which means that women are not born 'women' they rather 'become' women due to the social system of sex. Therefore, as Cheryl Clarke asserted: "gender oppression"

relies on “male exploitation and control of women’s productive and reproductive energies on the specious basis of a biological difference” ; In this respect, it can be argued that the biological categorization and division of sexes defined the ideology behind male dominance and gender oppression, since the disparate representation of sexes made it easier for men to take advantage of and bound women to roles and realities that further devalued and dehumanised them as the "other" gender. These incidents, as previously indicated, must be comprehended in the context of how women were frequently subjugated as objects of sexual desire by the male-dominated society, that additionally utilised them as reproductive commodities to build communities and subjected them to conditions and limitations they were unable to overcome.

Moreover, the dialogue between queer theory and feminism led to the creation of questions raised against heteronormativity and the formation of heterosexual relationships in the cultural system. The discourse around it continues to showcase the interconnections of gender, heteronormativity and the concept around male dominance; and the argument around why gendered ideologies were created, whether they are meant to exist or contribute to the generalised idea of a male society to assure men’s dominance, and consequently creating a marginalised space for the “second” gender, namely women, making them a subordinated gender devoted of value, or is the primary idea of gender is to serve a heteronormative system in order to exclude other minorities, bodies and identities. Naturally this conversation in both theories debates the initial ideology of gendered sexes and argues that they were configured by society in order to serve either factors, ultimately, serving a gendered idea of humanity in favour of men, and degrading women and other minorities as a result by depriving them of choice and limiting their opportunity and roles in society. It can be said that gender in itself has several dimensions and cannot be defined by biological assumptions.

1.2. The Social Construction of Gender

The thesis of gender can reflect not only bodily differences but also personalities, roles, minds, and identities. Gender as well refers to the process by which the differences of sex are seen as a challenge, due to cultural restriction and social deployments. For instance, in school, media and other institutions, just as Rubin asserted, gender can be seen as a social interpretation of the two sexes. The term itself can also very much refer

to the performative roles imposed upon either sex, it is a performance, an enactment, a stage that symbolises cultural and social beliefs, elaborating on the definition of the terminology.

Joan Scott argued that gender can be perceived to be made of two ideologies and many subsets. They're all connected yet they are meant to be distinctive. For he claimed that gender is a method and a symbol to the concept of relationships, powers and dynamics; he asserts that gender contains four interconnected variables that are to constitute the social connections on the basis of the generated distinctions of both sexes. He claims that the first is the 'culturally available symbols' that elicit numerous (and frequently contradictory) perceptions. Secondly, he argues that the normative notions that offer assessments of the "symbols' meanings" in order to make an effort to restrict and confine their metaphorical potential; such concepts are mainly reflected in the political, educational and religious aspects. Commonly the process behind this variable is to take the fixed binary oppositions of gender that clearly states what it means to be male or female, or masculine or feminine.

Further, he elaborates on the third factor being the ideologies behind the social structure and the political systems, lastly, he assures that the fourth facet of gender is the 'subjective identity' of gender. He elaborates by stating that these identities that are perceived in society are often generated in a substantive manner and are ultimately linked to certain roles, social groups, activities and cultural representations that are peculiar to particular periods historically (1986). Therefore, it can be claimed that the concept of gender is impossible to operate without any of these variables, for they are interconnected to each other, for the ideology behind gender and the field around it can be seen as the articulation of power.

Nevertheless, the proceeded arguments above can also be seen to define the gender dimensions as not only the distinctions of gender that were articulated in an attempt to create a gap between women and men, but also as an index to implicate the inadequate concept to distinct women of different races, classes, ethnicities, and sexualities from each other. To elaborate further it is worth mentioning that the process of othering of gender doubles when it comes to Eastern and other races; Beauvoir's thesis on the second sex already illustrates the generating of the 'other' sex, devaluing them to a second gender, a subclass to the main and the "natural" gender of humanity;

similarly the process of othering seems to double on the same basis of gender among western women and women of colour. According to Audre Lorde this process is highly influential on the ideologies of feminism as it sets a large gap within the women's movements today. The articulation of power creates a gap between white and women of other races as their oppression is ignored due to the cultural, race and class differences (1984). Generalising women despite the elements of culture and different lifestyles naturally leads to the presumed ideas of social structures and ultimately dismisses their experiences as unimportant as invaluable. Moreover, it is argued by women of colour theorists that the distinction of gender and the focus on it led to the universalised idea of a particular experience that is often experienced by white middle class women in the Global North which consequently was perceived as the "normative" situation of women in general, and as a result ignored the experience and the struggles of 'other' women in other races, cultures and classes (Lorde, 1981).

As previously preceded, the distinctions of sexes as the main and "natural" discourse behind the power dynamic and gender, created a problematic issue in terms of unifying the woman experiences and resulted in a continued dominance of men in society, the question that remained here is, what can unify the womanhood experiences without considering the bodily differences as the definition behind women, and how can women find a common ground as a marginalised group without reclaiming the gendered conceptions that were amounted to be?, feminist theorists concluded that in this sense, the best way to unify women's experiences is by confronting the common issues and creating strategies to alter reality, in this case, language was seen as the most effective strategy to 'name' the undefined oppressions and experiences women experience on daily basis that do not amount to political agendas, despite its personal values. As Dorothy smith noted, the lack of language and voice led to many unnamed and various experiences in which women were silenced and deprived of the opportunities of speaking up (2002).

Elaborating on the same thesis, Lorde insisted that those 'new' experiences necessitated a new language utilised as a primary device to speak of those previous unspeakable experiences. It is important for women to acknowledge these experiences by using poetics in order to create change and connect these struggles onwards. For every truth that is spoken for according to Lorde those words are "to fit a world in which we all believed, bridging our differences" (1984). Lorde viewed language for women as

a tool of transformation rather than of a luxury. For she asserted that it is a primarily “necessity” of womanhood. She believed that language leads to changes and hence opportunities, for poetics start as words, then form ideas and eventually lead to change and action. She elaborated that language is a way to give a voice to the voiceless, a name to the nameless and an ear to hear the unspoken, to put it in her words she believed that “The farthest horizons of our hopes and fears are cobbled by our poems, carved from the rock experiences of our daily lives” (1984).

Therefore, it is vital for women to reclaim language as a tool to recognise their voices after it was used as a tool to silence them all along. Reclaiming language, according to Lorde, is a way to transform silence to words and thereafter, those words are to be actions towards change. The examination of each experience, whether political or personal, is equally as important in order to commit to change

1.2.1. Patriarchy: The Political Repository of Classism

It is important to acknowledge the immediate impact of gender distinctions throughout the globe and the interconnections between it and classical patriarchy. As was the case pointed out, Gayle Rubin's work should be taken into account when analysing the manner in which gendered roles are expanding throughout society and each community. This is because, rather than being a simple action taken in public spaces or political movements, the ideology behind patriarchy can be seen to be articulated within smaller operations within households, communities, and cultures. It is crucial to take into account that women who were subjected to classical patriarchy—or who are subject to it today—often live in communities that are more culturally dominant. It is difficult to argue against the widespread application of cultural ideals as a means of subjugating women and placing them under control mechanisms that follow the lines of religious and cultural beliefs.

Many instances can be amounted to this, such as girls traded away for marriage at very young age groups into households that were dominated by their husbands' parents and male family members, these actions were meant to extended the control of girls and subordinate them not only under men's control but also elder women of the community, naturally, such examples did not only stop on constraining them but also subjecting them to many other conceptions such as honour and similar cultural ideas.

While classical patriarchy operates in small threads and lines as mentioned previously, its impact is inevitable on woman, for that does not only influence their livelihood within the personal boundaries but also limits their chances outside their communities, including working outside domestic boundaries and serving their families and husbands along with being seen as reproductive tools and nothing more. Women were and still are subjected to such restrictive livelihood due to those practices which led to further silencing them and taking their chances of experiencing social spaces, thus, they become more exploitable and put in a loop that is unchangeable due to the limited options they are offered.

Moreover, when classical patriarchy is in the picture, many women are devalued and therefore, unable to ask for compromise and see the roles they were subjected to as obligatory, and further, it becomes impossible for them to pressure or muster enough courage to demand any opportunities outside what they were given, for that can be deemed as disrespectful and crossing their boundaries. Consequently, they are led to believe that their silent 'resistance' can be seen as a good bargain for they reassure themselves that the silence offers them protection and thus, it is fair to be submissive and a propriety in exchange.

The foundation of gender division can also be tracked down to the history of materialism and the essence of Karl Marx's theories. Notwithstanding Marx's inability to recognise gender as one of the roots that enhanced capitalism and the economic structure of society. It is important to acknowledge that gender is also a very significant element that was built within the foundation of the capitalist system that was once deeply examined. To understand the associations of gender to economy, it is critical to understand the economic structure of society. For when men engage in specific, voluntary, and important relationships during the social production of their lives. These relationships reflect a particular stage in the growth of their financial productive powers and abilities. Those production interactions can be seen as the essence of the economic structure of said societies, it is the actual basis upon which the governing and legislative superstructures are built, as well as certain social consciousnesses (1995).

The general processes of life in society, politics, and academia are conditioned by the manner of production of material life. Opposite to popular belief, men's consciousness is determined by their social existence rather than the awareness itself.

Thus, it is easy to assert that a person's class and position in society is decided according to their position in relationships to the dominant system of production in specific time periods. Marx claimed that capitalism is a system of two ways, firstly the working class, the people who cannot claim or own the capital and are made to only have their forces of labour to make it in life, which leads us to conclude that the second class is naturally the capitalist class, as opposite to the working class, they are namely the 'bourgeoisie', whom have the rights to the capital and hence the means and force to dominate and exploit those who are of the working class.

As preceded earlier, while Marx and the Marxists were able to acknowledge the classism and the normalised ideologies of capitalism, they blatantly ignored the connections and the powers of reproduction, defining it as a natural social set for women and thus they saw the system of patriarchy as a normal practice despite the way it subordinated women and excluded them from being acknowledged as another class in the economic system.

Nonetheless, Hartmann, an American feminist economist, elaborated on those findings and argued that it is important to acknowledge that the foundation of patriarchy has interconnections with materialism; for men are able to control women's sexuality and means of gaining any resources. Unlike Marx, who saw the sexual division of labour as a natural fact, Hartmann argued, similarly to Gayle Rubin, that this division on the basis of its creation is a social concept. She refers to the underlying framework of patriarchy as the "sex/gender system" and describes how it limits women's lifestyles, body and sexuality and access to many opportunities in order to maintain male dominance. Furthermore, she concludes that socialism cannot end women's subjugation because it is not a product of the capitalist class system alone. Thus, feminist theories and activism ought to continue existing as a necessary element for change.

Similarly, Monique Wittig, a prominent innovative writer and lesbian feminist, elaborated on the oppression within the material context. She argued that it is important to define and acknowledge the persecution faced within the financial terms and refer to women as a class on their own. She claims that "the category "woman" as well as the category "man" are political and economic categories not eternal ones." (1992), and that by redefining women as a class, the feminist fight towards the sex division can be acknowledged as a political struggle against the superiority of the 'male' class that is

seen as dominant in social, political, and economic contexts. She asserts that with this 'fight' as soon as the class of men entirely disappears, the class of women is to evidently vanish as well, for she says, "there are no slaves without masters". She believed that it is important to distinct women from the definition imposed on them by social standards and redefine themselves as a class that does not associate with the 'normative' ideas that were employed in the 'mythical' term of women. She elaborates by referring to that definition of women as an 'imaginary formation' and a product of social relationship imposed upon them, thus that mythical idea of womanhood, does not in fact exist, it is man-made. Therefore, it is vital to recognise that class, gender, and race were all products created and interconnected on different levels to assert a male dominated and structured society. In other words, our society can be defined as patriarchal. Such a definition is evident when considering the modes of power not only on bodily terms, but also in political, economic, scientific, educational, and financial standards. Simply put, every power and force that creates society is entirely controlled by men, thus, the classism, genderism, racism are all interconnected within the context of the social powers, which can be seen as the pillars of a male dominant society.

Patriarchy in general can be defined as a set of social relations between men that are created on the basis of materialism in its origins, which causes an established trust system between men that leads to their interdependence and solidarity; ultimately enabling them to subjugate women. Patriarchy can be seen as a hierarchical system; however, it is also important to note that race and class as well as ethnicity all play a role in dividing these men in different places within the pyramid. Nonetheless, despite the level of distinction the male group is to be unified when it comes to establishing their dominance towards women. This dominance can only be realised by a shared systematic dependence between them. It can be said that the hierarchical system imposed by patriarchy allows those of power to 'buy off' those lower in class but at the same time they are able to offer them the power to dominate lower groups, which in this case, can be namely the group of women. Thus, despite the rank acquired by those men depending on the factors of race, class, and ethnicity, they are still enabled to impose their power on some women and isolate them as a group.

Therefore, it is vital to acknowledge that the basis of patriarchy, be classical or social, is all depended on the systematic trust founded by the male group in order to maintain their power and control over women, so it can be claimed that the current

definition of society is patriarchy, and without patriarchy, the commonly shared ideology behind society would not exist, thus society too, is no longer; at least when applying the common conception of social roles that is.

Thereby it could potentially be claimed that the institutional authority created by men to dominate women's labour is the foundation for the materialist underpinning of patriarchy. This would encompass the limitations placed on women, which make it difficult for them to obtain essential resources for manufacturing. For instance, this is reflected in women's jobs and salary to this day, this comes along hand in hand of course, with the initial control of women's sexuality, as a case in point would be the ideologies behind heterosexual marriages that are employed by culture and social roles, which allows men to control women's sexuality on the basis of serving them and reproduction, these serves linked by a thread of subjecting women to do unpleasant tasks that limit them to access the outside world, and employ humiliating services as their duty and roles such as domestic work and roles that include cleaning toilets and public spaces, whether it's in family settings or outside. By subjecting women to these roles, society normalised and thus limited their job opportunities to careers and tasks like that. For instance, it is common to see male bosses demanding women for exploitive services that can be as small as getting them coffee and cleaning, and as big as expecting sexual services from them (Henley,1977).

Moreover, those tasks do not only stop on physical labour but also physical appearance, a typical case would be the sexualisation of women's appearance in everyday jobs such as being secretaries. Furthermore, reproduction of babies can be considered as an immediate limitation of women's livelihood, and it is vital to acknowledge it as a task that feeds the foundation of patriarchy as a system. For the ideologies of classism can be applied in this sense on women, for they are expected to bring up the children and thus, are inferior to men, this can be linked to the social classism, for it extends to the way children are viewed as a product of control over women by a male led society. Due to such conceptions, it is normal to see men rarely involved with their children and are expecting of women to raise their offsprings according to the gendered roles of society, so each child is classified in the hierarchical system depending on their gender. According to Nancy Chodorow (1979; 1995) the social training theorems is overly simplified and cannot adequately account for gender differences. She, instead, contends that gender can be narrowed down to the masculine

and feminine characteristics that are acquired from early childhood depending on the common and traditional parenting styles. To be specific, the idea of gendered personalities often emerges from the reality of women being typically the primary carers for their infants.

The theorist elaborates by asserting that the psychic development of male and female children generally differs due to the fact that mothers tend to take care of them in a sole manner. In short, mums commonly relate and identify with their daughters than the male children, which can lead in different kind of relationships with their children depending on their gender, as a result, this creates a subtle outcome of mothers encouraging their sons to psychologically separate from her, causing a different strict establishment and well-defined ego boundaries created by him (1979).

On the other hand, mothers in this case, unintentionally prevent their daughters from having a separate personality or living as individuals unlike the sons, which results in unstable ego boundaries in their case. Chodorow maintains that the ego is often created unconsciously. Additionally, the gendered childhood socialisation builds on and reinforces the mothers to produce divided masculine and feminine individuals. Nonetheless, Chodorow asserts that despite those gender disparities being common, they ought to be altered. For the masculine and feminine binary causes a shortage of emotional expressions for males and hyper dependence for women. Moreover, the foundation of these divisions is created to oppress women. Those stereotypes can be un-achieved by involving both parental parties according to the theorist, she believes that would help contribute to preventing prevalent gender stereotyped actions by ensuring that children acquire sufficiently individualised senses of self without being unduly distant (1979).

Similarly, many outside institutions assert that these gender roles are continuously learnt and retaught in order to maintain the social distinction of both genders, this can be seen in religious institutions such as churches, in political institutes as well such as armies, as well offices and most importantly health care institutes and media. Therefore, it can be said that the foundation of patriarchy is not only hyper dependent on rearing children, but it also extends to most if not all social spaces, which automatically keeps women under control. This all can be considered to go hand in hand

with Gayle Rubin's theory as mentioned previously, as she identified these elements as a sex/gender system.

Nonetheless, these conceptions behind patriarchy and society can only be seen as a mass evidence that supports Rubin's thesis, while we are born as male and female, biologically, the set of both genders can be seen as a product of society, we are thus, made to be women and men. Therefore, it can be said that the way people meet their desires, the way the reproductive system works, and the social conceptions and norms set are all seen to be within the systematic labels she defined as the sex/gender system. Rubin places an enormous value on the role that family plays in determining one's capacity for sexual fulfilment as well as the "oedipal machine" and raising kids in the formation of gender-specific personalities. However, we may also analyse all other social institutions for their involvement in defining and maintaining gender hierarchies by using the concept of the sex/gender system. It can be hence claimed that both the interdependence of women and the systematic pyramid of classes among men and the subjection of women as a gender are the fundamental of the social structure created by humanity, consequently, these relations and dynamics can be seen as systematic rather than natural.

1.2.2. The Interconnections of Location, race, nation to the Gendered Modes

Examining the relationships between race and gender within the patriarchal system is crucial. Just as race influences a man's position in the pyramid, it also has a significant impact on where women are positioned—not just as 'women,' but as members of a particular ethnic group. This is consistent with Lorde's theory because, as was previously mentioned, the debarment of women's experiences from the context of location naturally undermines feminism as a whole and separates women into even smaller groups than the 'generated' category. For this reason, it's essential to take into account how location, nation, and culture affect women's status in gendered spaces. To elaborate further, it is important to view the initial articulated dynamics of gender in the commonly accepted perspectives; it is hence vital to acknowledge the roles imposed on women in various nations including third world nations, women's burden in this sense, can be seen as often complex than not, for women are meant to not only carry the

traditions of those nations, but also become a symbol, a representation to what we could refer to as the 'betweenness' of colonised nations; the representation of course in this sense is expected to be carried by them in specific procedures that would still carry the respect of their original traditions without discarding them, along with westernised modesty and ideologies. The impact of nationalism does not only employ symbolic duties on women but also limits their access to modernity and other lifestyles in order to keep their traditions in check. Feminists such as Huda Sharawi elaborated on these conceptions by indicating that those dynamics that are disguised as rights can be defined as public duties initiated on women in order to limit their rights rather than help them in achieving the desired lifestyles they would want. Women are expected to be modern but also not break from their traditions and cultural ideologies, thus, women's identity of these nations end up being stuck in 'between' in order to symbolise the nation and the links between traditions and modernism. As a case in point, women's position in the hierarchical pyramid does not only depend on the distinction of western and eastern races but also the nationalist ideologies imposed on them within their cultures; ideologies of nationalism regarding gender differences within the constitute are equally important for the display and structure of femininity and masculinity performativity within the nation.

Consequently, it is imperative to take into consideration the divergent viewpoints that the country has established regarding 'women' and 'men'. The aforementioned concepts serve as the primary basis for the notion that 'men' are perceived as the originators of national history, or, to put it another way, that men are seen as the nation's agents while women are only symbolic beings. These national ideas can be seen to be employed in many nations' ideologies, for instance, in many countries, whether in the Middle east or European countries back in the war times, women were expected to be a symbol of virginity, reproduction and to be faithful, meanwhile, men are viewed as the 'heroic' agents that are meant to fight bravely, protect and be the nation's foundation. It is vital to investigate the tip of the iceberg before moving to the bigger part of it, in this sense the significance of such nationalist ideologies extend not only within the nations but outside as well.

The process of othering women as a gender can be seen to double when considering the bigger scope of social conceptions that are created to perceive other nations. In order to dive into greater depth, it's critical to investigate the connections

between gender and postcolonial theories, since they both provide a more comprehensive understanding of the ways in which women are viewed as the lesser, doubly inferior other by both their country and the colonisers. For example, Edward Said's study of Orientalism exposes negative attitudes or prejudices about indigenous women. Thus, Orientalism has promoted female scholarship and discourse in Middle East studies (1978). Similarly, Audre Lorde's letter in "Age, Race, Class and Sex, Women Redefining Differences", she sheds light on the consequences that arose from dismissing the complexity and overlapping of women's identities. She asserts that the focus on women without considering their race, class or sexual preference can be critical to the movement in both the impact and the desired change. In her words, she declares that "Ignoring the differences of race between women and the implications of those differences presents the most serious threat to the mobilisation of women's joint power" (1984).

Therefore, the key to realising the problem is by acknowledging the complexities that come with race and stereotypes imposed on women of different races, thus, the differences Lorde refers to are not the same as the gender distinctions, but the racial experiences and complications that come with being a woman of colour. One could refer to these two ideas of difference as "actual difference" and "stereotypical difference." Furthermore, a close analysis of Lorde's usage of the term "difference" reveals that, in contrast to appeals to stereotyped difference, which reject all similarities, including the shared experience of being human, real differences must be recognised through a delicate balancing act that views variety in the context of a shared experience. (Piazza 2021). Nonetheless, the significance of realising these distinctions is meant to at least, reposition women on the hierarchical patriarchy system; in the sense, that women need to alter the ideologies that divide women in terms of race in order to undo the process of othering and the devaluation of women's experiences in spite of location.

1.3. Redefining Gender: the Enactment of Being

Notwithstanding the idea that sex is a stable binary in our time period, gender theorists believe that it does necessary imply that the gender of 'women' can only be understood by the female body, nor does it mean that men will only be constructed in the relation of the male body. Moreover, there is no crucial purpose or a reason to

presume that gender should stay at two, a binary, regardless of whether the sexes' structure and composition seem to be unproblematically binary (Butler, 1990). The assumption of a binary gender system perpetuates the notion of a mirrored relationship between gender and sex, in which gender either mimics or is otherwise constrained by sex, should the unchangeable nature of sex be questioned, it's possible that the concept of "sex" is just as culturally produced as gender. Thus, it is theorised and believed that there should be no relation between the definition of gender and sex, for it would imply that sex is a cultural interpretation just as much as gender and would be itself a gendered category. Therefore, it is argued that gender should be defined as a cultural subjection of meaning on pre-given sex. Hence, if one were to doubt the immutable nature of sex, one could argue that 'sex' is as much a product of culture as gender.

Judith Butler's theory of gender, which builds on Beauvoir's concept of the second sex and the othering of women, is primarily based on the contention that the framework of the binaries of sex and gender, the unequivocal of sex, and the internal ideologies imposed regarding gender are regulatory deceptions that solidify and normalise the converging power regimes of heterosexist and masculine subjugation. In her book *Gender Trouble*, she makes an effort to evaluate the concept of gender and raise a question—a trouble—by contesting these accepted and normalised concepts of gender, which are thought to be the cornerstones supporting the stability of heterosexist institutions, male authority, and masculine hegemony. Butler prefaces her theory by establishing that gender can be seen as a performance; which cannot be individual, it is a performative act that is both repetitive and done in a ritualist manner, naturally leading to successful long-lasting effects undergoing its 'naturalisation' in context of the body; in a culturally sustained secular structure. According to her, gender should not be seen as a performance that a person merely selects; these acts, which are "compelled by social sanction and taboo" gender one's consciousness and, in fact, one's physique. The idea that we articulate a gendered identity through complying with it is a fabrication of liberal rationalism. As an alternative, she contends that gender is "in no way a stable identity or locus of agency from which various acts proceed; rather, it is an identity tenuously constituted in time—an identity instituted through a stylized repetition of acts" (1990). Nonetheless, it is also vital to consider that gender is also a "myth" that we, the audience, and the performer, take for granted.

Butler moves on to state that another effect of the heterosexual social compact is that gender is defined as a binary of basic characteristics that unify biological sex, gender, and sexual preferences; this can be understood as the purpose of gender establishment being the development of bodies into distinct sexes in order to maintain 'natural' heterosexual proclivities. Gender performances therefore build and repeat the fictional reality of two separate opposing sexes that eventually and naturally come together to create a basis of the unity of society—the heterosexual family. Butler asserts that gender reality is thrown into disarray, meaning it is difficult for an individual to tell what is real and is not, thus, this can be recognised as the juncture at which we should realise that what society consider to be 'real', what we summon as an understanding of gender that has been normalised and naturalised as a 'fact', is actually a reality that can be subjected to revision.

Butler believes that these gender identities can be subversive. Therefore, a profound alteration in one's knowledge of what is conceivable and real is necessary for any political revolution, even though "this insight does not by itself constitute one". Occasionally, this change results from specific behaviours that take place before they are formally theorised and force us to reconsider our fundamental concepts, such as what gender is, how it is created and reproduced, and what its potential is. It is now accepted that gender 'reality', which has become entrenched and reified, can be created in a different and, in fact, less violent way. Butler contends in her book *Gender Trouble*, similarly to the earlier point discussed, that sexual orientation, gender, and sex are all seen as fundamental characteristics in Western civilization. She asserts that biological sex is binary—male or female—natural, necessary, and the foundation of binary gender, which is understood to be the way society interprets sex and sexual desire.

To put simply, the pre-selected sex of each person as a newborn, is dependent on their genitals; those selections extend to the individual sexual preferences, gender roles and sexual orientation in society, thus, she claims all these acts are linked together to achieve a certain order in society. This view of gender, as a social construct-based concept, is traced back to many feminist theorists and writers such as Gayle Rubin, Simone de Beauvoir and many other scholars, who also asserted that sex should be considered as a biological trait while gender is totally a culturally made product. Butler, however, argues against the idea that sex is wholly biological, and she believes that just like gender, it has culturally imposed elements on the basis of its definition. She

maintains that the idea behind this distinction is rather meaningless, she follows up this claim with much amassed biological evidence that does not necessarily align with the sex binary. Her perspective on this matter seems to increasingly align with modern scientific data as of lately, thus, there is a possibility in viewing sex as a spectrum rather than a definitive concept of biology.

Though to clarify, Butler's argument does not involve claims regarding the existence of biological processes or their impact on anatomical or hormonal variations. Instead, she contends that society's view is the only source of body reality and that this misunderstanding leads to simplistic, binary conceptions of sex (Morgenroth, 2018). In simpler words, the idea of a "natural" and separate binary of individuals cannot be recognised as a scientific or a biological process alone. The idea of seeing the two sexes as the norm or absolute mainly arose from the socially created gendered environment. More precisely, the possibility of two inherent, intrinsic, pre-meandering sexes seems feasible because of the recurrent performance of two polarised distinct genders (Morgenroth, 2018). Butler's thesis behind her work is that gender can be seen as a mere self-invention or that the presentations of gender can be deduced from its surface.

Furthermore, Butler's theory vacillates between viewing performativity as linguistic and perceiving it as dramatic at times. She thus believes that the two are inevitably connected, she maintains that idea by exemplifying the reevaluating the speaking act as a means of power, which highlights its linguistic and theatrical aspects. Butler therefore argues that gender is performative, having been constructed by its own performance rather than being necessary or physiologically established. The word "performativity," which first appeared in Austin's (1962) research on performative statements, describes speaking acts or behaviours that really produce the object they are meant to portray. For instance, in addition to describing what the speaker is doing—pronouncing something—the line "I now pronounce you man and wife" establishes the marriage—the object it is pronouncing—through the speaker's declaration. Butler expands on this research by examining how gender functions similarly—that is, how gender is produced by its own expression (Morgenroth, 2018). Butler also touches on how power seems to function in the creation of that extremely binary framework for contemplating gender, rather than just as an interchange between subjects or a relationship of perpetual inversion between a subject and an Other. What power

structure, she questioned, creates the subject and the Other, the binary relationship between "men" and "women," and the internal consistency of those terms.

Likewise, Simon de Beauvoir appropriates and reinterprets the hermeneutic tradition's defining actions thesis when she asserts that "one is not born, but, rather, becomes a woman." In this regard, gender can be defined as a label that is constructed seemingly throughout time; establishing an identity via a patterned recurrence of acts rather than a stable identity or a core of force from which different acts emerge. Furthermore, gender can be interpreted as the everyday ways whereby bodily actions, expressions, and legislation of different sorts create the appearance of an enduring gendered self since gender is established via the ornamentation of the body. With this framework, the notion of gender is no longer based on an adequate model of identity, but rather necessitates an understanding of formed social chronology. More importantly, gender is appropriated as manufactured when it takes forms of inwardly fragmented acts, making the essence seem to be fabricated; a performative achievement that the general public learns to believe and act in accordance with. Hence, it can be said that if the refined repetition of acts throughout times serves as the foundation for gender identity rather than an apparently seamless identity, then the potential for change in gender can be found in the inflexible relationship between these acts, in the potential for an alternate type of repeating, or in a rupture or subversive repetition of that style (Butler, 1988). Nevertheless. It is vital to note that the naturalistic interpretations of sexual orientations and sex, which presume that one aspect of women's anatomy may explain the significance of their social existence, have frequently been criticised by feminist theory. Just like Butler, many theorists challenged the causal explanations that presume that sex mandates or requires certain social significance for women's experiences in order to separate sex from gender. Likewise, many phenomenological theorists on human interactions examined and raised questions concerning the impact of the physiological and biological elements that articulate the sex existence and bodily differences in the context of experience. For instance, Maurice Merleau-Ponty, a French philosopher, argued that the body, in its sexual form, is rather a historical idea, taking in account the bodily experiences. He denies the idea of the body being a natural concept. Simone de Beauvoir's thesis is assumed to be built on that specific perspective, for when Beauvoir came forward with her theory, she reclaimed the same ideology, stating that the body is a historical product rather than an absolute fact. Therefore, phenomenological theory of

constitutions generally explains the complexions of the body in its process of adaptation, which can be described as a methodology of integrating certain cultural and historical possibilities (Merleau-Ponty, 1962). Some perspectives of configurations have led to the broadening of the traditional definition of actions; to include both that which produces meaning and the procedures by which meaning is expressed or performed in order to characterise the gendered embodiment. Simply put, performative activities in theatrical contexts are akin to the acts that determine gender (Butler, 1988).

Moreover, despite Beauvoir's assertion that women are a historical ideology rather than a natural factor, she does not dismiss the differences between sex, as a biological verity and gender as a socially constructed binary. However, she maintains the thesis that being a female notwithstanding those distinctions as a verity has no significance, yet to be a woman is having to become one, she claims that being a woman can be seen as compelling the body to embody those historical and cultural ideologies and symbols. The concept behind a 'woman' is to force the body to conform to cultural ideologies which in return forces the individual to submit to a historically determined notion; to perform this idea as a continuous, repetitive physical endeavour. Gender, therefore, can be interpreted as a performance with definite disciplinary outcomes as a survival strategy, that can be noted in nowadays cultures and societies; the distinctive genders play a significant role in how an individual is perceived, specifically as a human and the extent of humanisation applied on them depending on their gender. In fact, 'transgressors' of those gender roles and traits face regular consequences as seen daily. Gender, hence, can be considered to be something far from an absolute fact. The whole concept seems to rely on a series of acts that are merely gendered, and without those acts, gender as a notion can be easily discarded. Consequently, gender does not reflect nor externalise a certain core nor strives to an ultimate purpose or an ideal. It is merely an articulated category with concealed origins. The legitimacy of its own manufacture obscures the implicit shared commitment to perform, generate, and maintain separate and polar genders as cultural narratives.

According to anthropologist Victor Turner's research on ritual social drama, social acts seem to demand a recurring presentation. This repetition serves as the banal and ritualised form of a set of meanings that have already been socially established; it is both a reenactment and a re-experiencing of those meanings. Similarly, gender seems to adapt the idea of social performance as a tactic in this sense, so it becomes evident that

while the individual bodies can illustrate these significations by the process of stylisation themselves into certain gendered roles, the action is instantly visible to outsiders. Therefore, while these performances have social traits, their public nature also has its outcomes. Simply put, the thesis behind these acts is preserving gender within its binary boundaries and structure. Which evidently showcases the social laws that need to be adapted.

Additionally, Beauvoir emphasises that the body is subject to a particular cultural construction when she maintains that women are merely a historical concept. This is because the body is subject to conventions that not only authorise and prescribe how one acts in relation to one's body, or the "act" or performance that one's body is, but also to implicit conventions that govern how the body is regarded in society (Butler, 1988). Therefore, it can be also claimed that sex and gender in this case cannot be distinguished within the context of culture for gender is the cultural significance that the sexed body adopts; that is considering the influence of diverse behaviours, acts and the cultural perception. As a case in point, large scale political enactments such as women's careers, the inequality of rights and the extreme preconceptions in both legal and political discourses can all be seen as contributions to the reproduction of gender identity. Nonetheless, the more commonplace replication of gendered identity, however, occurs as a result of the many ways that bodies are acted in accordance with the profoundly ingrained or established demands of gendered life (Butler, 1988). Likewise, the heterosexual interconnections to the imposed gender and sex roles in society should be considered, for It is an unsustainable combination of cultural rules serving reproductive objectives when a natural sex is associated with a defined gender and with an apparently natural "attraction" to the opposite sex/gender. According to many researchers on kinship and feminist cultural studies, customs govern cultures by ensuring and regulating 'production, transaction, and utilisation of material goods as well as perpetuating the ties of kinship itself, to the extent of demanding taboos and punitive legislation or reproduction (Butler, 1988).

In summary, it can be claimed that the reality of gender is rather performative, which is to say that it exists only insofar as it is enacted. Thus, is it a valid argument to assume that some behaviours or 'acts' are typically meant to be perceived as an expression of gender, its core or identity; these behaviours thus, either support or struggle against the gendered classes that are imposed on them. These demands are

predicted on the basis of how sex is perceived, where sex is viewed as the distinct and factual datum of the main sexual traits. Gender exists regardless of the various stances, gestures, and acts that are utilised to describe and dramatize it, according to the commonly accepted view that interprets actions and gestures as conveying gender. In popular culture, gender is really seen as having a considerable core that could be understood as the spiritual or psychological counterpart of biological sex (Butler, 1998). Nonetheless, if the characteristics of said gender are performative rather than expressive, they can be interpreted as to make up the identity they are meant to reflect or disclose. It is vital to distinguish between expressionism and performativity, for the fact that if gender acts and attributes—the different ways in which a body expresses or produces its cultural meaning—are performative, then there is no preexisting identity by which an act or attribute can be evaluated; there are no real or distorted acts of gender, true or false, and the idea of a true gender identity is exposed as a regulatory fiction. The fundamental concepts of an essential sex, a true or enduring masculinity or femininity, are established as part of the strategy by which the performative side of gender is obscured, given that gender reality is created through persistent social performances (Butler, 1988). The truth-and-false narrative that gender is pressured to adhere to not just contradicts its own performative fluidity but also reinforces societal norms that regulate and enforce gender roles. People who misrepresent their gender are subject to a number of both immediate and secondary repercussions; on the other hand, those who accurately represent their gender feel confident that gender identity is crucial. There should be enough proof suggesting that there's a social awareness that determines whether the reality of gender is solely a matter of social convention rather than a moral requirement, given how easily fear can overcome this sense of security and how easily society criminalises, or eliminates those who are contrary to the deception of gender fundamentalism (Butler, 1988).

2. CHAPTER TWO: Circe: The Voice of the Voiceless

2.1. Circe: The Bodily Confinement

As a retelling, *Circe* highlights the feminine body from the moment the protagonist recounts her living circumstances. It is vital to first explore the idea of the female body via a theoretical lens given the entire novel provides a thorough perspective on the physical constraints and the metamorphosis that results from being a "nymph" and then a "witch." It is evident from reviewing the narrative that Miller wanted to draw attention to the physical circumstances of her characters as one of the primary themes that would ultimately assist and define the character's development. The protagonist states right away that she already occupies a limited role for a nymph meant not only a 'Goddess' but also a 'bride'; the author utilises that fact in an immediate manner to illustrate the boundaries of an already decided fate:

WHEN I WAS BORN, the name for what I was did not exist. They called me nymph, assuming I would be like my mother and aunts and thousand cousins. Least of the lesser goddesses, our powers were so modest they could scarcely ensure our eternities. We spoke to fish and nurtured flowers, coaxed drops from the clouds or salt from the waves. That word, nymph, paced out the length and breadth of our futures. In our language, it means not just goddess, but bride. (p.6)

Gayle Rubin's thesis on disparities in gender and her notion of the systematic gender/sex structure may be readily juxtaposed with Miller's decision to begin the book by highlighting Circe's role as a nymph in her familial circle. The word "bride" is used to refer to her limited status as a female goddess in her family and is a reflection of the social structure that serves to both perpetuate and establish families by providing for the "sexual needs" of the other sex. Miller's method seems to show the precise social structure in the mythology right away as a foundational idea, which she subsequently employs her heroine's metamorphosis to expand on. Nevertheless, she provides a full overview of the gendered modes of the world setting by highlighting women's places within the system and how they limit them to certain roles that are 'finally' traded as 'objects' by males in order to fulfil them and build communities. This is evident from on, as Circe's parents' marriage serves as an example of the predetermined fate of all nymphs. Perse, Circe's mother, was a prize to her father Helios, the Sun God. When Helios showed signs of interest in Perse, her father traded her and gave her to him right away, saying, "She is yours if you want her" (Miller, 2). Furthermore, this can be seen

when Circe describes the conditions of her birth, she illustrates how, despite not being a male, her family immediately saw a future in trading her to ‘men and gods’ who would want a chance to ‘breed’ from their family’s blood:

‘A girl,’ my mother said to him, wrinkling her nose. But my father did not mind his daughters, who were sweet-tempered and golden as the first press of olives. Men and gods paid dearly for the chance to breed from their blood, and my father’s treasury was said to rival that of the king of the gods himself. He placed his hand on my head in blessing. (p.4)

From her birth. Circe was already viewed as a product of trade for men, having no control over her fate or any choice to her own future. Miller showcases how Circe was subjected to being a commodity, and despite all, her worth was too little, her value amounted to her birth conditions and prophecy as an immortal daughter who’d marry a mortal prince. Nymphs were viewed as worthless, if not brides, or beautiful, as her brother Aeetes says:

Even the most beautiful nymph is largely useless, and an ugly one would be nothing, less than nothing. She would never marry or produce children. She would be a burden to her family, a stain upon the face of the world. She would live in the shadows, scorned and reviled”. Circe was not only viewed as worthless due to her prophecy, but she was also seen as ‘ugly’, her voice was described as horrifying other immortals, she was the least desired, not even as a wife. (p.61)

Throughout the first sequence, Miller depicts Circe’s life in detail as a nymph, when she eventually discovers her abilities as a witch or a ‘Pharmakis’. Ironically, her abilities stemming from her desires to her first love, Glaucus. A mortal, a fisherman who worships her. She eventually transforms him into a river god using her herbs, although he was unaware that it was her abilities that made him into a powerful god. Regardless of everything, Miller portrays Circe's disinterest in her abilities as a Pharmakis, given that those abilities could easily free her from her helpless status as a bride. Instead, Miller emphasises her desires to fulfil her role as a bride nymph, which can be interpreted as a reflection of how women's limitations in society can easily manipulate their sense of self-worth, only allowing them to submit to the standard gendered modes they are offered:

I longed to tell him that it was I who had given him such a gift, but I saw how it pleased him to believe his godhead wholly his own and I did not want to take that from him. I still dreamed of lying with him in those dark woods, but I had begun to think beyond that, to say to myself new words: marriage, husband. (p.52)

This corresponds to Beauvoir's theory of the second sex, according to which a person ‘becomes’ a woman rather than is one. As previously stated, Circe's ignorance of her witchcraft power structure and her will to perform the role of nymph that was

imposed upon her from birth illustrate how being a woman is a learned, as opposed to an innate, attribute (1949). This can be taken into account when navigating the idea that Circe's magical abilities represent a new reality because, after becoming a witch, she is no longer a nymph. This is consistent with the assertion made by Jacques Derrida in his essay "Plato's Pharmacy" (1981) that "Pharmakon makes one stray from one's general, natural habitual paths and laws." Circe's power and magic removes her from the limited position imposed on her and hence, gets her out of the gendered modes that she is confined to. It can be easily said that her magic does not only reshape her but transforms her completely, therefore, her reality as a nymph is invalid, in fact, she becomes a threat to the systematic patriarchal structure that was imposed on her the moment she gained powers that she should not have, as a bride nymph.

Thus, Circe's initial unawareness, and her desire to fulfil her role, can be easily seen as a manipulated ideology forced into her livelihood since birth. Her obliviousness and the way she feels the necessity of completing her role as a nymph can be examined using Butler's idea on the process of enactment. In this framework, it can be said that Circe's repeated acts of searching for a husband, discarding her power as a witch and her desire to be loved can all go hand in hand as a performance to achieve the approval of the general public—her community's approval. On the other hand, Circe's magical deed was already a tipping point that revealed the possibility of a different kind of performing gender; hence, it was a subversive repetition that might alter society's gendered norms. Miller's retelling can be said to have immediately embodied a breaking point for the character's development, for she does not only utilise her power as a motif for her transformation, but also simultaneously proffers her character. With abilities thought to be exclusive to male heroes in the ancient stories, Circe's strength in this area was already a means of subverting gender stereotypes in favour of her character, while paradoxically using the enforced gender roles as a justification for doing so.

In classical literature, magic in its essence was deemed as a threat when those who acquire it were meant to be marginalised. Historically speaking, the connotations of magic and gender were always regarded as a binary that should not be utilised. This can be traced back to the ideology of witch-hunting and its relationship with the patriarchal domain of society. According to Stratton's thesis in "Naming the Witch", she suggests that magic, in its essence, was viewed as a dangerous symbol of power to those who are outside the already founded roles of power, thus, it is ultimately threatening for

those who are not of authority to acquire it. In fact, it rather creates a source of ‘othered’ danger—in this case women, who are seen as the second sex to men (2007). Additionally, Stratton claims that, the exclusion of women in the domain of power was seen as a motive to seek power elsewhere, in this sense, ‘magic’ was associated with women as a gendered evil source of power that women acquire by executing unnatural rituals (2007). Hence, magic was seen as a fount for women to empower them in a way or another, and that would deliberately break their imposed roles in society.

In this sense, Circe’s magic was automatically deemed as a threat to the already established position that nymphs were subjected to, therefore, when the revelation of Circe’s deed was executed, she was ridiculed for her action rather than praised. Miller showcases the ways that Circe, as a female character, was not only regarded in a very limited stereotypical way — as a jealous woman, but it also illustrates the immediate way her power created a disorder in her environment and was regarded as a danger that needs to be put under control. Miller’s portrayal of the sequence and the aftermath can be clearly considered in terms of the gender agenda that is imposed on women. As mentioned before, women, as a sub gender, are not meant to have power in order to maintain the sex/gender system. Therefore, Circe’s banishment for having magical strength, regardless of how the source of power was created because of her desperate attempts to conform to the social roles, is seen as an obvious damage control attempt to contain the social structure of the environment she spent her livelihood in.

To fully comprehend Miller’s worldbuilding and the evolution of her protagonist, it's also critical to take into account the other "mortal" attributes that Circe was linked to. This can be interpreted in light of the world’s mythological framework. It is crucial to keep in mind that in classical literature, having mortality was viewed as a vulnerability. For this purpose, even before Circe was connected to magic, her description was very human. Case in point would be her voice, it is described as screeching and ugly, and it automatically made her less desirable and heard. Simultaneously, her voice reflects her physical appearance and thus, she was invaluable as a bride, automatically making her worthless as an object of trade. That is repeatedly implied and is explicitly shown when her siblings ridiculed her: “Father cannot even give her away. Believe me he’s tried” (p.28). Furthermore, her mortal characteristics are initially illustrated as a reflection of helplessness and the limitations that were drawn around her life as a female nymph. In the initial sequences, Miller weaves her character’s

circumstances into the very limited roles she was offered as a female character, specifically, in the way she constantly reminds the readers that her character is no more than a bride. This can easily mirror Beauvoir's thesis on how women are repeatedly dehumanised, in the sense that women are limited to the physical attributes they have and are defined by them as a sub gender (1949). The devaluation of Circe thus, can be viewed as a crucial aspect that Miller utilises as a prominent motif in the retelling later on.

Withstanding the fact that Circe was viewed as less desired due to her 'mortal' features, Miller does not fail to point out the ways Circe tried to weaponize her body in conjunction with her witchcraft in order to get what she desired; this is shown when Circe tries to use her femininity and her physical appearance to manipulate her uncles into giving her the answer to her prayers, after realising she knows where the gods' blood lies in her father's hallways. This follows Stratton's thesis as she asserts in her work that women, who used witchcraft, were also seen as deviant for having their own desires and used their feminine physical attributes in order to obtain what they desired (2007). In this sense, Circe falls into the stereotype of those classical witches:

I had learned something from my mother after all. I bound my hair in ringlets and put on my best dress, my brightest sandals. I went to my father's feast, where all of my uncles gathered, reclining on their purple couches. I poured their wine and smiled into their eyes and wreathed my arms around their necks. (p.39)

It is vital to understand that while Circe's act was to fulfil her role as a bride nymph, it served as a rebound to her role as a female nymph as her usage of magic was a start of a transformation of her identity outside the boundaries of her initial role. This is deliberately shown when she does not only fail to be acknowledged by her first love, Glaucus, but also in how her power is received by her father, Helios, and her family. When Circe turned Scylla into a monster, she not only failed to be seen but also put Scylla in the same position as hers, creating a new victim. Circe's hopes to be acknowledged laid in the way she transformed her cousin nymph in order to be desired. However, the heroine failed to realise that she was already seen as damaged goods, and that Scylla's transformation only reflected her position. Glaucus, indifference to her love and efforts mirrors the way male characters, be a god or a mortal man, view women as objects to be traded, this follows Gayle's thesis on the trading of women and the way it serves the gendered system (1975):

I heard Glaucos' low voice: 'Can she not be changed back?' Every god-born knows that answer from their swaddles. 'No,' my father said. 'No god may undo what is done by the Fates or another god. Yet these halls have a thousand beauties, each as ripe as the next. Look to them instead.' I waited. I still hoped Glaucos would think of me. I would have married him in a moment. But I found myself hoping for another thing too, which I would not have believed the day before: that he would weep all the salt in his veins for Scylla's return, holding fast to her as his one, true love. 'I understand,' Glaucos said. 'It is a shame, but as you say there are others. (p.5)

It is also important to navigate the choice of words Miller utilises to showcase the devaluation of female characters. As perceived in the dialogue above, the way Helios talks about the nymphs can be seen as objectification. Miller's usage of 'ripe' and the mention of 'thousand others' back-to-back illustrates a small picture of how women are perceived in the sense that they were always up to trade.

Additionally, this exchange illuminates the fact that Circe's attempts were all to no avail because she was already perceived as damaged goods. Moreover, Miller elaborates on that notion with the revelation of Circe's power. Circe's hopes to be accepted and heard by her father immediately backfire, counter to her wishes. Her confession to her deeds does not only cause a disorder, but it starts a witch hunt against her later, for she opposed the natural order of her familial role. While her father deemed her confession as a foolish lie that she made up as a jealous nymph, he takes the matter seriously when her brother Aeetes, goes to their father, and tells him that he and all his siblings are Pharmakis. Miller depicts the way Helios does not take chances, or even shelters his daughter, instead, he perceives her and her power as a chaotic consequence that needs to be put under control. Thus, while her brother was given the freedom to rule the lands he was given, Circe was sought to be punished and banished for performing witchcraft willingly, despite her efforts being to achieve her duties as a bride nymph.

Furthermore, Miller's depiction of Circe's voice is very important to examine in order to understand her character. Throughout the retelling, Miller utilises Circe's voice as a motif that serves as a device that helps Circe find her identity. Nonetheless, it is vital to analyse the way her voice was illustrated in her early livelihood before her banishment, that is specifically in the ways it was described not only as human, but also the lack of its usage throughout decades. It is perceived from the earlier chapter that Circe's voice sets her apart from the other gods and divine creatures, not only that, but also, she spends most of her time silent in her father's hallways throughout the first sequence. There were many instances where she was ridiculed for her mortal toned voice. However, it is inevitable to realise the way her voice reflects her powerlessness

as the story develops. Miller's usage of Circe's inner dialogue mirrors how Circe was not used to being heard, nor has she felt that she is allowed to speak. This specifically aligns with the feminist researcher, Dorothy Smith's statement that: "We discovered that we had been in various ways silenced, deprived of the authority to speak, and that our experience therefore did not have a voice, lacked indeed a language" (1990) Instead, it is notable that Circe's desperate attempts to be validated came from her silence. She utilised her quietness in hopes to be seen by her first love, Glaucus and her father Helios, as well she sought protection by submitting herself to her role as a damaged bride. However, it was to no avail.

This premise readily mirrors Lorde's contention that poetics is essential and that personal experiences must be acknowledged on an equal basis with political ones (1984). In this sense, Circe's experience is seen to reflect the way women weaponize their silence as a form of 'resistance', in the sense that it is a good bargain for them to be quiet. Nonetheless, Circe's silence served as quite the opposite. For she was perceived as damaged goods and no less.

Miller's usage of language and her depiction of Circe's inner thoughts are seen as vital, for she does not only offer a small picture of how silenced Circe was, but also, how her voice was already a symbol of her powerlessness because it was already deemed as worthless. The author does in fact, weaponize the negative connotations to her voice in order to navigate the way her character was silenced early on, easily showcasing the struggle of women as a sub gender: "Circe," he said, when he saw me. Just that, as if you might say: foot (p.56). Throughout the first sequence, the usage of language and the ways nymphs are described — despite their divinity— always reflected a lesser value to the other male gods. Furthermore, Circe's attempts to be heard were immediately shut down as feeble attempts of a jealous 'witch' rather than as equal. The reaction to her deeds towards her cousin, and her attempts to please both her father and Glaucus, were rather seen as evil attempts to create a disorder, and thus, she was deemed as a threat. Miller displays that in the way Zeus and the upper gods were involved. All in all, Circe's existence was a political and a social threat in the systematic pyramid, therefore, she was sent away in order to keep her contained, rather than having her influence those around her, which would put everything out of order.

2.2. Circe: Aiaia: The Rebirth of the Body

Circe's isolation in Aiaia, allows the heroine to regenerate her identity as a whole. Miller navigates the cruciality of Circe's isolation for it does not only serve as a new beginning, but also it is an act of unshackling herself from the imposed gendered system that she was used to. Aiaia, immediately serves as an embodiment of an environment that is free from the gender system and the discourse of the second sex. Miller, thus, deliberately utilises the world setting in her favour in order to develop her heroine and further explore her identity without the limitations that she was bound to.

Not only does Circe appear to be overwhelmed upon her banishment, but she also appears unable to comprehend how to survive on the new island. Circe's proposals in the sequence mirror her ignorance and powerlessness. The author leverages Circe's incapacity to rely on herself for survival right away to highlight the consequences of the restrictions that existed in Circe's prior surroundings. Her inexperience and helplessness underscore the processes in which nymphs were indoctrinated to serve men exclusively, marry men, and acquire the knowledge of appeasing the dominant gender alone:

I hesitated. I was no wood-nymph. I did not have the knack of feeling my way over roots, of walking through brambles untouched. I could not guess what those shadows might conceal. What if there were sinkholes within? What if there were bears or lions? I stood there a long time fearing such things and waiting, as if someone would come and reassure me, say yes, you may go, it will be safe. (p.68)

Circe's assumptions and her faithlessness in her bodily capabilities serve as a reminder of how she perceived herself as a female nymph, her worries showcase how women are taught they're lesser for their bodily features and thus fragile. Moreover, as she ascends and finds it in her to explore the island, Circe slowly understands the fact that she was a tool to restrain her father and a device to be used by the male gods. Her thought process mirrors the hierarchical structure of her previous environment, as well the fact that she was always meant to be perceived as an object in one or other. The realisation of her position further helps her understand the manner in which her role in her family was always to serve her father's powers, instead of her own. She was a symbol of his power and pride, a political hostage in order to fight for more dominance:

Zeus had demanded the discipline of Helios' blood. Helios could not speak back openly, but he could make an answer of sorts, a message of defiance to rebalance the scales. Even our exiles live better than kings. You see how deep our strengths run? If you strike us, Olympian, we rise higher than before. That was my new home: a monument to my father's pride. (p.69)

Miller exposes the unvarnished reality of Circe's existence—that she was always there to subordinate and maintain the authority of those male characters in her life. But considering she was alone on the island; she was able to express herself through her body in ways she had never been able to before. As a consequence, the island allowed her to reinvent herself as it freed her from the constraints of the gendered system, which required her to conform to predetermined roles and serve men. This is also grounded on Beauvoir's statement that "The fact that she [women] accomplishes nothing, that she is nothing, will make her impulses only the more passionate. Empty and unlimited, she seeks from within her nothingness to attain All" (1949). Therefore, Circe exploited her lack of knowledge and skills to assist her rediscover who she was, comprehend how her body functioned, and unleash the powers that others saw as an imminent danger:

"The worst of my cowardice had been sweated out. In its place was a giddy spark. I will not be like a bird bred in a cage, I thought, too dull to fly even when the door stands open. I stepped into those woods and my life began" (p.83).

It is important to navigate the source of Circe's magic, for it can be easily differentiated to the powers of the other divine gods and goddesses. Although Circe's magic was clearly awakened by instinctive thoughts, Miller illustrates that her power was not simply acquired, and that it is to be learnt. In this sense, considering Circe's provocative motives is crucial as her magic came to her when she was in a conditioned position — out of desperation, therefore, it is vital for her to unconditional herself to those roles in order to learn her magic. Miller already implies that Circe had the knowledge of her magic beforehand in an innate level, however, she showcases how she was degraded by her brother for not being able to wield it. Aeeses Claims that one cannot learn sorcery and that it comes from within, but that could not be applied on Circe for she gained those magical skills through her desperate attempts to fulfil her womanly role, thus, her magic was not initially obtained through normally conditioned circumstances. Consequently, Miller utilises that factor in order to showcase not only Circe's independence in her island, but also as a huge motif that reflects her journey to rebirth her identity. Circe's attempts to learn magic can hence be considered as her undoing her conditioned poisons in a metaphorical and literal sense: "No wonder I have been so slow, I thought. All this while, I have been a weaver without wool, a ship without the sea. Yet now look where I sail" (p.84).

Circe's ability to relearn magic and wield her powers in an unrestrained island depicts a beginning for her to discover herself in an unconditioned manner, which allows her to understand both her body and her capabilities as a nymph goddess. Miller especially highlights her journey from the very beginning in order to showcase Circe's development and her growth into independence. It is extremely important to keep in mind that Miller does not attempt to weaken her character in order to give her more authority. Rather, she uses the most humane portrayal of Circe to demonstrate her will. The fact that the heroine accepts rather than discards her body is crucial to her evolution because it shows how women can achieve power without having to conform to the stereotype of the "general gender," or male, as Beauvoir would put it (1949).

Alternatively, Miller's approach clearly works on humanising the female experience when given the freedom of accessing all sources with no boundaries. She tries to display a human rather than a sub humanised image of womanhood, in order to undo the enactment that is imposed on their livelihood. Her approach likewise adheres to Butler's philosophy of gender unravelling through act disruption (1990). Miller employed the remote island to provide the ideal setting for her character to defy gender norms and become an ideal embodiment of herself. In this regard, she allows Circe to break from her gendered body, without disposing of her femininity and subverting her into the other gendered role, which in this case would be the male gender. The heroine thus, adapts to her new life and relearns magic and finds herself independent opposite to her doubts towards her capabilities, which in this sense, can be seen as a slow undoing of her learnt roles as a bride, and a transformation for her identity.

The character herself grows acutely aware of the oddities that were taught to be normal in her prior context. She ultimately learns to deal with the concept that she was just as capable as people who, in their strength and dominance, seemed invincible. Circe discusses the irony of having spent thousands of years believing that she was neither entitled to nor capable of holding authority. She illustrates how the male characters in her life dehumanised her to the point where she was unable to comprehend or acquire knowledge on her own. Nonetheless, her banishment served as a blessing in disguise, for she managed to not only break the boundaries of her gender, but also learn to become an equal to those she once considered above her:

I brought a withered flower back to life. I banished flies from my house. I made the cherries blossom out of season and turned the fire vivid green. If Aeëtes had been there, he would

have choked on his beard to see such kitchen-tricks. Yet because I knew nothing, nothing was beneath me. (p.87)

Furthermore, in Miller's approach to Circe's journey as a witch she ensures that her character does not dissociate herself from her female body, in fact, she utilises witchcraft in a way that reflects her womanly attributes. Miller's usage of language takes advantage of the ways witches are negatively associated with women, and she uses that to her advantage to reshape the way Circe views herself. Witchcraft in the way Miller tells it, does not in any way hold onto the connotations it has with evil and the villainising notion of women. In fact, Miller highlights her character's optimistic outlook on her new identity by illustrating the sense of accomplishment that comes with practicing witchcraft, particularly when she finds herself in a precarious situation where the need for survival becomes paramount. The author additionally utilises Circe's first encounter with a wild animal as an important instance that demonstrates the heroine's strength and how it knows no bounds:

He stamped, and the white foam dripped from his mouth. He lowered his tusks and ground his jaws. His pig-eyes said: I can break a hundred youths and send their bodies back to wailing mothers. I will tear your entrails and eat them for my lunch. I fixed my gaze on his. "Try," I said. For a long moment he stared at me. Then he turned and twitched off through the brush. I tell you, for all my spells, that was the first time I truly felt myself a witch. (p.89)

Furthermore, it is vital to keep in mind that Pharmakeia (magic) was already seen as a threat and an evil source of wickedness in the early chapters, that is perceived when examining Circe's interactions with her grandmother, and how it was explicitly a taboo subject for them. As discussed previously, sorcery in its essence has its negative connotations with women as a source of evil as it is seen as an act of disorder, that is seen in the manner Circe was dealt with when her father banished her. Nonetheless, it is important to navigate Pharmakeia as a motif that is used to highlight the way Circe was constantly silenced in her previous settings. To elaborate, it is important to consider that Circe's initial goal was to be seen as she was never heard, and as indicated above, in Circe's thousands of years of living, she was continuously living in silence, that kept in mind, Pharmakeia here, can be seen as a symbolic device that Miller uses for Circe's voice, hence, it was perceived as a threat because Circe's silence was no longer easily achieved. Her magic offered her a source of voice, a language in which she can speak for herself, and as a result, chaos and disorder to her environment that was strictly built on silencing female nymphs and goddesses. In this regard, Circe's 'ugly' mortal voice

was not the only source of voice that Circe attempted to use to be heard, her magic can easily go hand in hand with her mortal tunes.

Nonetheless, Miller here offers a new song for Circe in her isolation. The heroine's ability to wield her power is an explicit demonstration of Circe's singing, her freedom to act, move and practise all allowed her to use her body and physical attributes in her favour without being unable to access any of them. This is also demonstrated in the ways Circe's new magic in its essence, offers her the power of birthing, transforming and shifting her creatures. Her tamed lioness is a strong symbol of Circe's capability to speak for herself. The fact that she summoned her own lion, showcases an outrageous factor in Circe's ability to control life, in the sense that women's roles of production lie on their role to please and give the male sex families and create new communities. However, Circe's ability to grow her plants, give life and transform creatures is a powerful indicator on how she achieved a freedom that is beyond the conditioned roles of the gender system, therefore, the character continuously reminds us that her capabilities would send her father and brother in disdain and rage for she is going against the natural order of their structure.

Miller further, goes as far to make her character sing, she transforms the way Circe's mortal voice was a symbol of her silence to something that symbolises her freedom. Circe's literally finds herself seeking to sing in her island, while she reminisces the manners, she was not allowed to sing for her voice was hideous to those around her. She sings her spells she sings in her work, the repetitive act of singing can be seen as a representation of her free will and the lengths they reach, as well an ironic indicator of how little of freedom she had in her family halls, Circe's acknowledgement of her boundaries further helped her to cross them, she found a sense of empowerment as she allowed herself to do things that limited her abilities to be ever heard. The heroine also acknowledges how her transformation would deliberately cause a chaos and a disorder in her family hallways:

I could imagine what my cousins would say if they saw me: my feet dirty from working in the garden, my skirts knotted up around my knees, singing at the height of my frail voice. I wished that they would come. I wanted to see those goggle eyes of theirs as I walked among the dens of wolves, swam in the sea where the sharks fed. I could change a fish to a bird, I could wrestle with my lion, then lie across her belly, my hair loose around me. I wanted to hear them squeal and gasp, breath-struck. Oh, she looked at me! Now I will be a frog! (p.89)

Moreover, Circe's connection to her voice and magic reflects the manner in which she creates a connection with her body. Her magic thus, is as connected to her body as it is to her mental powers. Miller specifically highlights that in the ways Circe uses her body for physical labour in her land in order to create more spells, the way she sings her magic to come true, and further the manners in she connects to her island. Aiaia, therefore, becomes a mirror of her isolated yet freed body, she becomes one with what she was subjected to. she reshapes the borders in which she thought she was contained, and instead finds ways for herself to transform her environment into what suited her best. Circe's singing thus, is a breaking point that entirely represents her freedom, unlike the ways in the original myths, where she is perceived to lure men with her singing voice. Miller utilises her voice as a powerful symbol that displays her character's growth onto freedom, she weaves Circe's negative attributes into a brilliant act of rebirth for the character and her identity, hence, her voice, much like her magic and body, were transformed to be sources of the character's comfort and quests to achieve her full rebirth. In other words, it can be said that Miller offers Circe the ability to use her own poetics and language to compel herself towards freedom and full independency, reshaping her idea of herself as damaged goods into a powerful witch, just as Bracke wrote in her analysis:

In the absence of a male guardian who might function as bard, they sing themselves, thereby appropriating a typically male manner of expression... That Circe can be "heard" sets her apart from normal women who are constrained by their male guardian: in the absence of a guardian, Circe acts as her own poet. (2009)

Circe's isolation thus offers the heroine the opportunity to experience her body fully with no restraints, allowing her to come in touch with the features of hers that were perceived as 'mortal' and weak. Her ability to connect with her body and the so-called weaknesses serve as an important development in the novel and helps her further in the quests she faces later. Additionally, her connection to her power serves as a problematic element and a threat to the overall social structure as it is at odds with the female body and the picture painted for womanhood.

2.3. Circe: Pigs and Men: The Patriarchy

Miller's retelling embodies many of the quests Circe encounters to help navigate the manner in which her heroine deals with the patriarchal elements that invade her

island throughout her journey. This chapter further argues the fact that despite Circe's magical powers and her independence in her island, the moment she is faced with patriarchal elements or makes a social contact she is bound to limited options due to the ways she is perceived by the other parties. To elaborate, it is important to examine the instances in which Circe specifically dealt with male outsiders coming to her land.

Miller deliberately makes use of Circe's banishment and her first experience on the island to showcase the fears Circe has. The heroine explicitly depicts her fear of being assaulted as a female nymph in the earlier chapters, illustrating the ways despite her divinity, she's subjected to the same fears living in the world of gods and men:

“I had not known how many things I feared (...) pirates muffling their oars in my harbour, planning how they would take me. And what could I do? (...) I would only be able to scream, and a thousand nymphs before me knew what good that did” (p.82).

The author frequently emphasises how women can become victims of sexual harassment, and Circe was the ideal example to illustrate this point. Circe affirms immediately that nymphs are viewed as gifts or as brides who should appease other males. However, men were able to perceive Circe as a potential trophy for their wants since her physical attributes were always seen as a representation of her inferiority as the weaker gender or sex. Classical literature specifically, employs female figures in order to buffer the main heroes and showcase them as winners. Therefore, characters like Circe were always meant to be seen as 'tributes' despite their will to do so.

As Circe embodies her powers and adapts to her new freedom and identity, Hermes, the son of Zeus, visits her island as the first outsider since her banishment. Miller explores the ways Circe welcomes the new visitor by illustrating how her heroine finds herself able to have a lover without the obligation of pleasing him. This is reflected in the way Circe is able to set conditions to her relationship by not willing to give children to Hermes, while this can be perceived as a small shift in her course of action, it is evident that Circe's freedom had helped her create a boundary of her own without laying herself as a naked prize. In this regard, it can be said that Circe's abilities to set conditions would have been seen as problematic in her previous environment. For instance, it was outrageous of her to attempt to pick her husband by asking her father to marry Glaucus; for nymphs in this case, were goods to trade and not seen as equal creatures to bargain with their fates. Nonetheless, Circe's capability to control that part

of her relationship in her isolation thus can be seen as a clever attempt to set new rules opposing the systematically imposed ones. Furthermore, Miller utilises Hermes, as a device to constantly remind Circe of Scylla, whom can be seen as a mirror of her guilt that stemmed from her rage and uncontrollable magic in her desperate attempts to conform to the role she was meant to fulfil, as well to remind her of the outside world she was once obligated to survive.

Withstanding these aspects, Miller also manages to showcase the way Hermes perceived Circe, while Circe showed control over her little bodily freedom, it is evident that Hermes himself does not take her seriously but rather as entertainment. Though in this case, Circe is much aware of that. It is important to navigate the manner in which the character manages to acknowledge the ways she's seen when facing these typical patriarchal perspectives she's subjected to. For while Hermes does not see her for her powers nor as an equal, Circe manages to control the parts she wants despite the elements of misogyny imposed on her. Miller illustrates her character taking advantage of Hermes as much as she manages to in order to satisfy her emotional and physical needs as well as a way to learn about the outside world:

I could feel his power reaching for my secrets. In the old days I would have rushed forth with a brimming cup of answers, to give him all he wanted. But I was not the same as I had been. I owed him nothing. He would have of me only what I wanted to give. I rose and stood before him. I could feel my own eyes, yellow as river-stones. "Tell me," I said, "how do you know that your father is not right about my poisons? How do you know I will not drug you where you sit?" "I do not." "Yet you would dare to stay?" "I dare anything," he said. And that is how we came to be lovers. (p.95)

Circe's understanding of Hermes, as a male god, can be traced back to the ways she was subjected to her father's dominance along with the other male figures in her life. Circe's: "I could feel his power reaching for my secrets. In the old days I would have rushed forth with a brimming cup of answers, to give him all he wanted" (p.95) heavily implies the ways women were trained to submit every part of them to the male power they are under. Miller's usage of language easily presents the fact that women feel the urge to please men with all their power in order to protect themselves, the author showcases that in the way Circe implies she once felt that she 'owed' them answers and they had every right over her. This sequence is vital to consider as it reflects the ways classical patriarchy works; the foundation of patriarchy is very dependent on the chain of power and dominance that men establish between each other to have women submit to them. In this sense, Circe's old life can be seen as a perfect model of this system. That

is explicitly seen when Circe's power transforms Glaucus to a god. By doing so, she gave him a position in the systematic power structure, and he thus became part of the same established pattern between the male characters. Such an instance is specifically shown in the way he shifts his personality and pays Circe back with utter indifference and sense of superiority. As soon as he was given a domain of power, Glaucus adapted the gender system that funds itself in perceiving women as subhuman or the lesser gender. He immediately finds himself looking down on Circe instead of acknowledging her love or efforts that she had previously shown, and he'd have enjoyed it.

Miller also handles the fact that "mortal men" with less authority are included in this framework. As the retelling reaches a set point in Circe's development and knowledge of her power, the author demonstrates how those "lesser" figures of power can be even more vicious with the power domain they were offered by the upper class — in this case, the divine male characters. Circe exhibits a highly pleasant attitude towards the mortal men that come to visit Aiaia. The character does not feel frightened by mortals given that she is at ease in her own flesh and on her native land. This is particularly crucial to take into account because Circe's voice and appearance have traditionally made her connected with mortals. Additionally, Circe's attitude also seems to mirror the fashion of which her island became a safe boundless space that has no connotations to her past:

I could not stop smiling. The fragility of mortals bred kindness and good grace. They knew how to value friendship and an open hand. If only more of them would come, I thought. I would feed a ship a day, and gladly. Two ships. Three. Perhaps I would start to feel like myself again. (p.85)

That sentiment, however, was short-lived considering the only aspects of Circe that the mortal visitors noticed were her gender and physical appearance. Miller uses the rhetoric directed towards Circe to embody this part of the novel. At first, the heroine finds herself delighted by the words of thanks given to her as the mortals named her a 'goddess', however, as their interactions continue, she finds herself realising that the titles they used were rather ways of flattery:

A knife fell to the floor, and I picked it up. When the captain's cup was dry, I filled it from the brimming bowl. He lifted it to me. "Thank you, sweet." Sweet. The word set me back a moment. They had called me goddess before, and so I believed they thought me. But they showed no awe or religious deference, I realized. The title had been only a flattering courtesy for a woman alone. I remembered what Hermes had told me long ago. You sound like a mortal. They won't fear you as they fear the rest of us. (p.89)

Nonetheless, Circe does not find herself shaken in the initial interaction, Miller instead displays how the character is more fascinated by mortals and is taken by her curiosity and love for friendships. Therefore, she does not consider the ways she is perceived as weak for being a lone woman in an empty island. The author navigates the fashion in which her character is perceived by the mortals, When the dinner starts, they start referring to her as "sweet" rather than as a goddess (p.185), which is reminiscent of Helios' remark that nymphs are "ripe" for men to eat (p.51). Circe finds herself slowly realising that she is then seen as a target of their desires as a woman, this is perceived when the mortals continuously question if there is any male figure that Circe belongs to. In an attempt to determine which man she belongs to, they first inquire about her husband, then her father, and finally her brother. Circe anticipates that they would be astounded to learn that she is an independent woman—a goddess even—whom they have been fortunate enough to dine with for she says:

“If you would thank your host,” I said, “thank me. This house is mine alone.” At the word, the air changed in the room” (p.189).

Miller demonstrates an uncomfortable realistic presentation of how women are used and taken advantage of. This aligns with Beauvoir’s statement that “The relation of woman to husband, of daughter to father, of sister to brother, is a relation of vassalage” (1949). As the atmosphere changes, she finds herself contained and restrained when she faces such danger, moreover, she is incapable of comprehending the position she's in, she finds herself in doubt and does not allow herself to question the shift of their attitude and the air:

I plucked up the wine-bowl. ‘It is empty,’ I said. ‘Let me bring you more.’ I could hear my own breath as I turned. I could feel their twenty bodies filling up the space behind me. In the kitchen, I put a hand to one of my draughts. You are being silly, I thought. They were surprised to find a woman by herself, that is all. But my fingers were already moving. I took the life off a jar, mixed its contents into the wine, then added honey and whey to cover the taste. I brought the bowl out. Twenty gazes followed me. ‘Here,’ I said. ‘I have kept the best for last. You must have some, all of you. It comes from the finest vineyard on Crete.’ They smiled, pleased as such solicitous luxury. I watched every man fill his cup. I watched them drink. By then each of them must have had a cask in his belly. The platters were empty, licked clean. The men leaned together, speaking low. My voice felt too loud. ‘Come, I have fed you well. Will you tell me your names?’ They looked up. Their eyes darted like ferrets to their leader. He rose, the bench scraping on the stone. ‘Tell us yours first.’ There was something in his voice. I almost said it then, the spellword that would send them to sleep. But even after all the years that had passed, there was a piece of me that still only spoke what was bid. ‘Circe,’ I answered. The name meant nothing to them. (p.189)

Miller illustrates the fact that the assumption that there is a male figure in Circe's life was her shield from getting taken advantage of. The moment she lost that security factor, she was immediately viewed as a prey to these male mortals. The shift of the atmosphere offers an uncomfortable image of the ways women are devalued the moment they are of free will. Circe being a lone woman, deliberately subjected her to the same system she left behind in her family's hallways, where she has been conditioned her entire life by men and their power, as well the fear of what they could do to her body. The moment Circe realises what is about to happen to her, she practically provides them drugs in the form of a draught that may make them all helpless and immovable. She even goes so far as to deceive the men into drinking the potion she has created with her hands, which is the material aspect of her Pharmakeia. Circe appears to know what is about to happen and is terrified of the rape that does occur. Miller uses this as a narrative of the incident that will eventually drastically change Circe's mental state. (Laseter, 2020). This follows Cahill's thesis on women who face rape, she elaborates on how the typical reactions of a rape victim are those of a person who should have known but temporarily forgot that she was always at risk, that the risk followed her everywhere she went, that it was inescapable. These reactions are characterised by tremendous remorse and self-loathing. For it is believed that she was attacked because she dared to think for even a split second that she was safe (2000). This can be seen to be the case for Circe, as she experiences the traumatic event, she is unable to forgive herself. It is clear that she finds herself angry with how she could not stop it, despite knowing it would happen. As a result, her sense of freedom and the unlimited source of power she thought she obtained for herself, take a drastic shift as a result of being violated. It is clear that Circe had confidence in her mastery of magic, her connection with her body, and her embodiment of her island, thus she created a safe space for herself, not considering the outer elements that come from different realities are meant to invade her secure space. Therefore, the traumatic experience she encountered served as a harsh reminder of the reality and the social system she once escaped. The heroine again, became aware that the island she made for herself was a separate reality that in no way and form can keep her safe outside or when dealing with outside elements. Miller displays the manner of which men feel entitled to women and their bodies completely solely due to the power they are offered by the system and structures of their societies. This is explicitly shown in the way they deliberately saw her as free goods as soon as they confirmed no one had the claim over

her 'ownership'. The moment she admitted to being the owner of her body, she became free goods to claim. A lone woman in her position would always be a prey, Circe thus, was always a potential victim, or as Cahill would namely call her a 'pre-victim' of rape (2000). The fact that she was divine did not save her from the destiny most women undergo, solely due to their gender and psychic.

The effect of Circe's assault caused a huge shift in her identity and confidence in her power, for the moment she got assaulted, she felt entirely subjected to the patriarchal power system all over again. This is demonstrated in her actions post the event, Circe's voice is strongest when she lives alone on her island; if she must return to society in any way, not even on her own, men can silence her voice and take away the power she gains by assaulting her body (Laseter, 2020). This is explicitly shown in the way Miller showcases how Circe's voice gets caught up in her throat as the man blocks her throat, stripping her from the ability to speak up, which was the only way she could have displayed her powers to stop them: "I had said there was no one on the island, but he had learned not to take chances. Or perhaps he just didn't like screaming" (p.189). The author here illustrates how she was rendered completely powerless due to the fact that the foundation of her power relied on her body, voice and mind. Once she was unable to use her voice, she was incapable of awakening her powers. She was completely silenced, shown in that scene solely as a woman, a victim, and a prey. This evidently shifts her position in power, and she is once again presented as the nymph she previously was: "I am only a nymph after all, for nothing is more common among us than this" (p.190).

Nevertheless, as the scene unfolds, Miller displays the fact that Circe finds herself hoping to be seen and acknowledged from the humiliation she was facing. Like the way she wanted to be seen by her father for what she has done to her cousin and for the sake of her love, she found herself contemplating whether her father would ever punish these mortals for what they have done to her:

It was shading to dawn, when the silver horses of the moon go to their stables. My aunt Selene's chariot had been full all night, her light strong in the sky. By the brightness of her face I had dragged those monstrous carcasses down to the boat, struck flint, and watched the flames leap up. She would have told Helios by now. My father would appear any moment, the patriarch outraged at the insult to his child. My ceiling would creak as his shoulders pressed against it. Poor child, poor exiled daughter. I should never have let Zeus send you here (p.190).

Furthermore, through this sequence, Circe understands that she had always been part of that society she thought she escaped. The event causes her to understand that she will always be exposed to those patriarchal ideas; even though Aiaia is a safe space for her, her rules do not apply to these mortals and visitors, for they come from those environments in which she is deemed unworthy, and they would always weaponize that against her. Miller thoroughly manages to navigate the reality of these male characters by using the tragedy Circe faces, it is indeed, a crucial step that she has taken in order to expose the social structure women are subjected to. It is an important reflection of many real experiences that women undergo, following Lorde's emphasis on the importance of poetics to acknowledge these personal experiences (1984), Miller sheds the light on it by using Circe's experience as a model to document these traumas.

The act of rape did not only silence Circe, but also reduced her to nothing but her feminine body, there for their sex and devoid of any uniqueness of her own. Immediately, Miller showcases her heroine using her sorcery to disembody them as a payback, she strips them from all their human attributes and mortal physical forms, leaving only the most repulsive phallic symbol. As Brilliant argues in his article "Kirke's Men: Swine and Sweethearts", that the image of pigs for men has a compelling intensity owing, undoubtedly, to the most 'piggish' behaviour of pigs, glutton and lust being their prominent qualities," They reduce to their screams, and she rejoices that they are audible again after being made to remain silent (1995):

Convulsively, I swallowed. My throat clicked. I felt a space open in me. The sleep-spell I had been going to say was gone, dried up, I could not have cast it even if I wanted to. But I did not want to. My eyes lifted to his ruttled face. Those herbs had another use, and I knew what it was. I drew breath and spoke my word. His eyes were muddy and uncomprehending. 'What ---' He did not finish. His ribcage cracked and began to bulge. I heard the sound of flesh rupturing wetly, the pops of breaking bone. His nose ballooned from his face and his legs shrivelled like a fly sucked by a spider. He fell to all fours. He screamed, and his men screamed with him. It went on for a long time. As it turned out, I did kill pigs that night after all (p.90).

Nevertheless, Circe's tragic event leaves a lasting scar on her sense of self, regardless of how she punished them. Similar to what many rape victims go through, Circe's violation resulted in a significant breakdown of power. Unable to break free from her experience, Circe resorts to acts of retribution in an attempt to feel better about herself. whilst she made an effort to break free from her gender roles, the assault served as a continual reminder that she would always be treated unfairly by the patriarchal system and seen as a woman first. At the end of the day, she was nothing more than her

physical attributes. Indeed, Circe even finds herself angry with herself due to the fact that she should have seen that long coming, as mentioned previously, women see themselves as pre victims to sexual harassment and train themselves to assume a day will come in which they have to accept their fates, Circe herself implies that she, too, should have known this was due, sooner or later:

Maybe the true surprise, I thought, was that it had not happened sooner. My uncles' eyes used to crawl over me as I poured their wine. Their hands found their way to my flesh. A pinch, a stroke, a hand slipping under the sleeve of my dress. They all had wives, it was not marriage they thought of. One of them would have come for me in the end and paid my father well. Honor on all sides. (p.192)

Consequently, her rage drives her to take revenge on most of the mortal man that would step foot on her island, by doing so, she hopes to provoke her father and Zeus by displaying her power and wielding it in rage, however, soon she realises that her victims and magic were not enough to have those male gods acknowledging her. Thus, she decides to employ those same abilities to disprove mortal men's perceptions that she was a woman before becoming a witch: "Let them see what I am. Let them learn the world is not as they think" (p.193). While Miller demonstrates Circe's rage in its extremes, she also displays how her character was not mindlessly raging her power at every mortal she encountered, the author showcases that when Circe says: "so grateful for my help. A few of these, so few I can count them on my fingers, I let go. They did not see me as their dinner" (p.194). Circe's trauma drives her character to relish in her power and thus causes her to anticipate what she would do next to those mortals who try to take advantage of her: "the next crew to come, so I might see again their tearing flesh. There was always a leader. He was not the largest, and he need not be the captain, but he was the one they looked to for instruction in their cruelty. He had a cold eye and a coiling tension" (p.194). Circe repeatedly tests all the mortal visitors that she encounters. She uses her singing to lure them, knowing they would not consider that she has any power simply because of her gender. Similarly to how she got raped due to her mortal attributes, her voice provided all these men the reassurance of how she could not possibly more than a woman, a feminine body and a prey. She utilises the exact features that caused her the traumatic event in order to trap men who would assume the same thing. She shields herself by the knowledge she gained with her experience, she reassures herself by doing so, they would never be successful again. Her human traits thus proved to be problematic in the sense that she uses them in a menacing way. Therefore, due to the revelation Circe experienced with her rape, knowing men

have no fear, she weaponizes their indifference to her advantage to make sure she is never seen as less again, she takes advantage of her power in order to spread fear and show herself as a witch to those mortals, as a reaction to her rape, Circe does her best to cast her self-directed loathe in an outward manner towards these men, in doing so, she thinks she will be able to come in term with her wounded identity again. Lascter argues in her analysis of the novel that:

Knowing she has the pharmakeia flowing through her veins, and she was able to drug the men without them becoming aware, flips the script and puts her in the place of the men's usual position. One cannot read these scenes without comparing them to a modern context, thinking about men in bars slipping drugs into a woman's drink and waiting for her to lose the ability to fight back. But even as she takes on the role of violator of bodies, Circe still does not hurt the men in a sexual way. Rape remains a female violation, and therefore she remains in the role of female body first and foremost and within the power structures always. (2020).

Therefore, it can be argued that Circe uses her loathing towards herself as fuel to deal with her rage with men from what she has dealt with for ages. Miller showcases how just as it was previously demonstrated in the first sequence of the novel, her magic reflects her desires, thus, it does not only cause transformation but also, her anger is reflected in her acts of sorcery. Her power becomes a source of protection for her against men's predatory behaviour, which causes her to lose her sense of liberation that came to her once she learnt magic. This thus served as a problematic reminder for her that is still restrained by men's nature, and she is limited to what they do. For at the end of the day, she is tradable goods for them. In other words, Circe's constant positioning as a woman prevents her from realising her full capabilities and using her magic in the world outside of Aiaia, Miller's revisit of Circe's most notorious acts, such as turning men into pigs, and uses a horrific scene of rape to explain her rage, achieves this notion as her portrayal of Circe as a victim, someone who is raped in the most hegemonic manner, unable to use her voice, and has her body defiled, showcases the fashion in which Circe's rage and unresolved trauma act as motifs to her actions towards men.

2.4. Circe: Motherhood, Birth and Womanhood

As indicated previously, motherhood and birth are often seen as the biggest elements weaponised against women in order to limit their life roles. Thus, as many feminists believed, women were seen as the product of reproduction and the gender/sex system in order to create families and communities. As stated by Gayle Rubin, the

ideology behind this social structure is founded on the basis of women being tools to create and give birth to keep the system going. Moreover, women are expected to embody motherhood as a full responsibility with the access of limited sources (1975). This is seen in the ways women were a subject of trade in many cultures that were built of patriarchal ideologies. Likewise, as Cheryl Clarke asserted, gender oppression heavily relies on the ways men exploit women's productive and reproductive powers; in doing so, women's roles are reduced to dehumanised and sexualised livelihoods that are bound to their biological bodies (1981).

There were two major events in Circe's life in the later sequences, the first being meeting Odysseus, who somehow helped her regain her trust in mortals, and find herself able to embody positive emotions towards him, and the second was the birth of the baby he left with her. Miller's approach to motherhood is rather distinctive; the author uses Circe's experience with birth as a careful navigation of the struggle that comes with being a mother, woman, and a parent, as well as an empowering interpretation of the extent the character is willing to undergo to fulfil her role in her own fashion. Circe's immediate understanding of her pregnancy was followed by her taking cautious steps to reassure herself of her experience. She sends all her nymphs to their fathers to be alone, as she is aware she is in one of her most vulnerable states. Circe then casts her spells in order to keep any outsiders away from her island, she ultimately assumes every possible way to assure her protection. Regardless, Circe's experience with birth showcases the ways women struggle the most, her lack of experience and help were all elements that made her birth harder, illustrating the dangers that come with the role of motherhood:

I knew so little of childbirth, its stages and progression. The shadows changed, but it was all one endless moment, the pain like stones grinding me to meal. I screamed and pushed against it for hours, and still the baby did not come. Midwives had tricks to help the child move, but I did not know them. One thing I did understand: if it took too long, my son would die. (p.241)

Nonetheless, as soon as she gives birth to Telegonus, Circe finds herself proud and considers her experience a statement against her father and those men that cast her away: See? I told him. We do not need anyone. In answer, he made a froggy croak and closed his eyes. My son, Telegonus." (p.242) It is important to consider the fact that Odysseus's absence, along with the mannerism in which Circe gave birth, Miller illustrates the ways that women often are left alone and expected to fulfil such roles fully on their own. Moreover, Circe's lack of access to sources, education and help can all be seen as a reflection of how women sometimes are left to handle the responsibility of

reproduction on their own without the male presence or access to medical help. Additionally, Miller elaborates with her thesis towards motherhood by detailing the ways Circe struggled with raising her child. As her son was also a mortal, she realises he necessitates far more than the divine children. Circe's fight throughout motherhood, illustrates not only the new experiences a mother could face, but also the difficulties that come with it. She comes to the realisation that despite all the power she gained, and all the enemies she fought, motherhood was a puzzle of its own, something on a totally different league:

I did not go easy to motherhood. I faced it as soldiers face their enemies, girded and braced, sword up against the coming blows. Yet all my preparations were not enough. In those months I had spent with Odysseus, I had thought I'd learned some tricks of mortal living. Three meals a day, the fluxes, the washing and cleaning. Twenty diaper cloths I had cut, and believed myself wise. But what did I know of mortal babies? Aeëtes was in arms less than a month. Twenty cloths got me only through the first day. (p.242)

Miller further utilises Circe's divine nature in order to showcase that even being an immortal did not make the struggle easier; despite the fact that she need not sleep or eat like mortals, she struggled to find moments of peace, she was filled with fears of harm that could come to her child and became more and more paranoid. The author not only illustrates the problems Circe faced but also touches on the psychological urges of a mother:

Thank the gods I did not have to sleep. Every minute I must wash and boil and clean and scrub and put to soak. Yet how could I do that, when every minute he also needed something, food and change and sleep? That last I had always thought the most natural thing for mortals, easy as breathing, yet he could not seem to do it. However, I wrapped him, however I rocked and sang, he screamed, gasping and shaking until the lions fled, until I feared he would do himself harm. I made a sling to carry him, so he might lie against my heart. I gave him soothing herbs, I burned incenses, I called birds to sing at our windows. The only thing that helped was if I walked—walked the halls, walked the hills, walked the shore. Then at last he would wear himself out, close his eyes, and sleep. But if I stopped, if I tried to put him down, he would wake at once. Even when I walked without ceasing, he was soon up, screaming again. Within him was an ocean's worth of grief, which could only be stoppered a moment, never emptied. How often in those days did I think of Odysseus' smiling child? I tried his trick, along with all the rest. Held my son's floppy body up into the air, promised him he was safe. He only screamed louder. Whatever made the prince Telemachus so sweet, I thought, it must have come from Penelope. This was the child I deserved. (p.242)

Eventually, when her son does in fact face Athena's attempts to have him die, Circe rejects her and somehow manages to stop Athena's direct harm towards him. Despite the offers of blessings and bribes that Athena made, Circe's motherly love does not shake, and she rejects every single bribe she was offered. Moreover, Circe's power witnesses a huge shift as it reflects her state of mind; as indicated previously, Circe's power, body and mind all interconnect in order to achieve her desired spells, in other

words, her identity is the source of her power. When Circe became a mother, her domineer reshaped itself as to what she prioritises and loves the most, in this sense, her son became a symbol of her emotional weight and her motherly love as well as her will to sacrifice. Thus, when Circe finds herself unable to give her son up, she manages to cast some of her strongest spells as of yet. The first spell would be her ability to stop anyone from getting into the island, and the second ensured that if she ever collapses due to her vulnerabilities, the entire island, including the landscape, must protect her son, Telegonus:

Athena would kill my child, and so I defend him," I cried. "Be witness now to the power of Circe, witch of Aiaia.-I marked them, and all the generations in their bellies, with Telegonus' name. If ever she did break through that smoke, the island would rise up in his defense, the beasts and birds, the branches and rocks, the roots in the earth. Then we would make our stand together. (p.255)

Telegonus exhibits a great deal of interest and affection for his father, who is absent, when his mother tells him about his father's adventures. Miller skilfully navigates Circe's parenting style and portrays the process of his development. Conversely, Circe never once shares information about herself or how she shields him. As her kid gets older, Circe understands that he will eventually elude her, that he has tried to enter the world she has kept him out of, and that he will eventually wish to see his father. When he first made contact with mortals, after convincing his mother, it is notable just as indicated in the previous chapter, fitting Nancy Chodorow's theory, the psychic development of her son as a male child, is seen to have reached a point in which he finds the need to separate himself from his mother, creating a well-defined ego boundary (1978). This is seen in how her son behaves, specifically in the instance in which he speaks over her, introducing himself as her son when the mortals talked to her, he already showcases typical patterns of the gendered role he would have conformed to outside the island: You are in the house of the goddess Circe, daughter of Helios, and her son, called Telegonus. We saw your ship founder and allowed you to come to our island, though usually it is closed to mortals. We will be glad to help you all we can while you are here. (p.265) This perhaps can be considered as a vital example of how Circe's lies to her son and her focus on talking about his father's quests, consequent in him looking up to his father as the only model of power and strength. It is important to note this as Circe found herself unable to give herself credits for anything she has done, in order to make her son happy:

I had not told him of his infancy, how angry and difficult it was. I had not told him the stories of the gods' cruelty, of his own father's cruelty. I should have, I thought. For sixteen years, I had been holding up the sky, and he had not noticed. I should have forced him to go with me to pick those plants that saved his life. I should have made him stand over the stove while I spoke the words of power. He should understand all I had carried in silence, all that I had done for his safekeeping. But then what? He was somewhere in the trees, hiding from me. So easily those spells had risen in my mind, the ones that would let me cut his desires from him, like paring rot from fruit. (p.273)

When Telegonus eventually decides to leave, Circe tries all that is in her power to stop him, but at the same time she could not bear the idea of making him unhappy as a result, she ultimately agrees to let him leave. Consequently, Circe immediately takes action to protect her son further, by giving him Trygon's spear, which she had obtained in order to keep her son alive. This is a vital point in the retelling because Circe's act of going to the depths of the oceans to acquire this spear reflects the lengths in which she had gone to keep her son safe as well as the fact that she achieved more than what a classical male hero would have achieved in their quests. Circe's character embodied many features of a typical hero but found herself undermining her achievements in order to highlight Odysseus' for the sake of her son. This serves as a very crucial aspect of how mothers and women are often underestimated despite all their efforts to be seen as equal, additionally it showcases the ways women themselves are often trained to view anything they do as an obligatory responsibility that has no value despite the difficulties that come with them:

I could not feel the knife handle in my hand. I could not feel anything. My son seemed distant as the sky. I lifted the blade, touched its tip to the creature's skin. It tore as flowers tear, ragged and easy. The golden ichor welled up, drifting over my hands. I remember what I thought: surely, I am condemned for this. I can craft all the spells I want, all the magic spears. Yet I will spend the rest of my days watching this creature bleed. The last shred of skin parted. The tail came free in my hand. It was nearly weightless, and up close there was a quality to it almost like iridescence. "Thank you,". (p.281)

Furthermore, her sacrifice clearly symbolises the extents of love the heroine had for her son, illustrating the importance of the emotional shift of Circe's, because she had not only found herself able to love someone in ways she was never loved, but also, Miller ensures that her character does not lose her feminine or empathic attributes in order to conform to certain heroic stereotypes. She embodies both her identity and equally achieves many heroic acts that would have been highlighted as legacies. This notion is emphasised by the knowledge that Circe's brother Aeëtes failed to earn the tail in the scene while she emerges victorious. When her son comes back, after long days of waiting, the revelation of his confession to accidentally killing his father sets Circe protective instincts to immediately makes her shield her child again.

Telegonus soon after reveals that he brought Penelope and her son home with him. This sequence at first might not seem essential to consider. However, with their arrival, Circe learns the full truth about Odysseus. She realises then the woman she was once jealous of, was in fact burdened with her marriage similarly to all the women she once had known. Miller navigates Circe's inner development of how she perceives these two intruders. At first, her motherly instincts kick in right away and she finds herself unable to trust them for she feared they would harm her son. Nevertheless, as she interacts with both characters, she finds herself unable to perceive Penelope and her son as threats, in fact, she grows to understand them, specifically, Penelope; "Odysseus had said about her once. That she never went astray, never made an error. I had been jealous then. Now I thought: what a burden. What an ugly weight upon your back" (p.332).

Circe begins to consider these people as many victims of their circumstances as she may have been Penelope carried the weight of Odysseus' ego and her anxieties that he would harm her son, while Telemachus was a victim of his father's aggression and paranoia. Even after his death, Penelope was burdened by the fates, the fear of her son being subjected to avenge his father by Athena, thus, she fled with him and Telegonus. Furthermore, Miller uses this sequence as a chance to utilise the relationship between Circe and Penelope, as their interactions increase, Circe is seen to come in terms with her identity. It can be argued that Penelope's appearance was meant to sort of stabilise Circe's fortitude in herself, for she saw a model of a woman that stood as firm as a pillar in Penelope:

I looked at her, as vivid in my doorway as the moon in the autumn sky. Her eyes held mine, gray and steady. It is a common saying that women are delicate creatures, flowers, eggs, anything that may be crushed in a moment's carelessness. If I had ever believed it, I no longer did. (p.317)

Ultimately, Penelope can be considered as a definite employment of power; in the sense that she too seemed to reflect a similar shade to Circe's life, while their circumstances were different, both women experienced confinement, were overshadowed by men and were subjected to the consequences of those men's actions.

2.5. Circe: The Conversation between Transformation and Identity: The Final Enactment of Breaking Gender

The premise of metamorphosis is the primary motif used by Circe in her retelling to convey the heroine's identity. The idea itself runs throughout the book and is undoubtedly the most significant representation of her effort to overcome her gender. Since it reflects how Circe breaks free from the constraints of her gender identification, it is crucial to take into account the relationship between this concept and her identity. To further explain, it is important to understand Beauvoir's thesis, which holds that a woman becomes a woman rather than being born as one. 1949 The concept of "becoming" eventually suggests the opposite of "originating something," and as such, Butler (1990) speculated that "intervention" might occur in the process of becoming. In this case, Circe's continuous transformations, whether it be herself or her environment, can be seen as evident interventions of her gender, thus she manages to reshape her identity outside the given roles. Moreover, as Butler argues in her work *Gender Trouble*, the notion of gender refers to entirely performative roles imposed on either sex, hence, it is an enactment on a stage set by either a culture or a society that believes in certain roles (1990). Therefore, when Circe was given the opportunity to leave the stage that was set for her, she was able to constantly transfer herself. Indeed, Miller employs not only her quests to aid her change but also, the fact that her magic in its essence was revolved around transforming other elements, was already a big symbol of her de-enactment, or in other words, her breaking from the imposed definition of being a 'woman'.

As the preceding sections have demonstrated, Circe's powers were seen to be problematic right away since they make her "unfit" to be a nymph. Her magic was "chaotic" in and of itself, but it's also vital to keep in mind that, given that it was linked to her mental state at the time, and thus it mirrored who she was as a person. Circe was already subtly defying the gender that society had assigned her since she was starting to desire Glaucus. Indeed, the fact that she was actually attempting to control her destiny was a sign of her transformation. Therefore, when Circe makes an effort to change her circumstances by transforming Glaucus as a god and wanting him as her husband, she had in fact created a menacing disorder within the social system she was part of. This is evident in the mannerism in which her father reacts to her desperate attempts to marry

Glaucos. The notion of a woman having a choice in whom she'd marry was an alien offence to her father's power domain and pride, and further, when she confesses to her magic and deed, she is set to be banished because her small shift of identity was deliberately perceived as a threat to the social gender system.

Moreover, Miller takes advantage of Circe's banishment in the island, not only as a new stage for her character, but also as a way to give her the ability to completely set her own rules. This is seen in the fashion in which Circe slowly takes charge of her own life, she finds herself slowly capable, as she states: "I have been a weaver without wool, a ship without the sea. Yet now look where I sail" (p.84). This shift in the environment is very crucial to consider as it plays the biggest part of creating a new identity foundation for Circe. The heroine's physical capabilities and mindset immediately reflected on her magic, the notion of transformation took its most evident part in the start of her banishment, this is notable in the ways she transforms not only herself but also in how she recreates her stage; the character transforms the wild animals and tames many companions, the most notable symbol being her lioness, moreover, the under-structure of her magic with herbs was heavily depended on how she reshapes them into magical elements that supports her in her identity journey. Simply said, Circe's first stage outside her original environment, was the biggest factor in her quest of undoing her gender. The enactment of independence was a very crucial step in her life as it allowed her to access all the sources possible without limitations. Additionally, she had no reason to keep enacting in the manner she was trained to act, which ultimately helped her detrain her mind and make her able to find parts of herself; the lack of the social structure and male dominance, hence, were perhaps the most significant factors of her identity change.

Furthermore, it is noted that the author intentionally weaponizes the notion of transformation throughout the retelling to help her character achieve her identity in an utmost level. Miller employs the motif in both its extremes, be negative or positive. It can be argued that by doing so, she manages to give her character the healthiest development that eventually leads to subverting her gender. While Miller utilises her character's voice and inner thoughts to her advantage, she also uses them as a device to showcase the character's shifts of emotions and state of mind throughout the good and bad sequences. For instance, Circe's directed anger on mortal men after being sexually harassed, explicitly showcases how she felt contained by the gender role she has been

trying to escape all these decades on Aiaia. Furthermore, it served as an important way to reshape her mindset and powers in ways that helped her destruct and re-achieving her identity; “The purple bruise at my throat was turning green at its edges. I pressed it, felt the splintered ache. Tear down, I thought. Tear down and build again” (p.193).

Additionally, when Circe finds bits of herself again, she enables herself to embody her emotions and fall for Odysseus, but it is vital to understand that all her actions in this sequence were all on her own terms. While Circe suffered heavily due to her traumatic experience, Miller showcases the fashion in which her character finds herself again. It is also vital how the author does not make her character discard her feminine and emotional attributes in order to heal. In other words, Miller’s idea of undoing Circe’s gender is not in any way an explicit direction towards the masculine ‘general’ gender, instead, she weaponizes her characters’ masculine and feminine features without degrading either of them and she translates her character in both her feminine and heroic classical characteristics. This is all perceived in the ways Circe finds herself constantly, makes her decisions and embraces her body and sexuality for herself. Therefore, when Telegonus is born, Circe’s journey regarding motherhood, is rather empowering. Miller’s navigation of motherhood is rather one of the most detailed sequences in the novel; that is vital to examine as the character not only shows the struggle of motherhood and birth in an explicit way, but also demonstrates the extent of sacrifice and love women can embody for their children. This is crucial due to the fact that women’s role as mothers is not taken seriously, further, women are limited to too little resources and are expected to employ certain roles on their children without considering their position in the family system. Therefore, Miller’s positive yet greyish approach to motherhood served as a very important stage of development in terms of Circe’s identity, for her whole domineer shifts and reshapes itself for her child and towards herself, it can be said that this is the stage in which Circe’s identity, reaches its maturity, for she accepts her womanly features and masculinity without having to conform to the gender structure.

Lastly, it is heavily vital to navigate the conclusion of the retelling in terms of its interconnections with identity and the notion of transformation. Despite Circe’s early relationships in life, when she falls in love with Telemachus and meets Penelope, she finds herself reshaping her desires to what she wants, and thus prioritises herself. She eventually realises that she was ready to confront the essence of her divinity in order to

achieve her desired self. Miller's last approach is rather brilliant because she weaponizes the idea of immortality and divinity and how these two reflect the vital unchanging factor of Circe, and that her desire to transform was only achievable when she'd undo that part of herself. This is crucial and is overshadowed throughout the novel. Miller weaponizes the character's mortal attributes and illustrates how they are the truest parts of Circe. Throughout the novel, Circe embraces her womanhood, and utilises her voice as her ultimate source of power, moreover, she witnesses a physic shift that would reflect her mortal features rather than her divinity. This is implied in multiple instances throughout the retelling, for example, when the mortals first visited, they assumed her a mortal rather than a nymph. Similarly, Circe is only shown to showcase her golden eyes and her true form in her rage. Indeed, Circe's mortality in this sense is seen as her truest unbudging parts of her. On the other hand, Circe's divinity was never perceived to be part of her journey. In other words, her immortality and divinity were rather the least of a reflection of her identity. Thus, when approaching the conclusion of the novel and Circe realises what she had truly desired to be, she manages to undo the parts of her that she was a subject to rather than part of:

Overhead the constellations dip and wheel. My divinity shines in me like the last rays of the sun before they drown in the sea. I thought once that gods are the opposite of death, but I see now they are more dead than anything, for they are unchanging, and can hold nothing in their hands. All my life I have been moving forward, and now I am here. I have a mortal's voice, let me have the rest. I lift the brimming bowl to my lips and drink. (p.388)

Circe's final transformation, thus, can be seen as the best vehicle for her to constantly be herself and reshape herself as a person. Her final undoing of immortality evidently reflects her complete undoing and rebirth of her identity. In this regard, Miller emphasises the fashion in which change is an ongoing process with no ends.

3. CHAPTER THREE: Ariadne

3.1. Limited to Crete: Ariadne: The Confinement of the Mind

Saint leverages Ariadne's perspective from the outset of her recounting to guide the reader through her surroundings and her approach to life. Like many classical myths, the author purposefully begins by recounting King Minos's accomplishments as a well-known hero, including the overthrow of the previous monarch, Nisus, and his conquering of the country of Megara. Saint's methodology intentionally illustrates how female characters were always intended to be instruments to further the narratives' protagonists. The author utilises Minos' heroic quest as an argument to introduce her notions in this manner. She demonstrates how Scylla, the daughter of Nisus, deceived her father to win Minos' love. However, as Minos triumphs, he drowns Scylla in order to display to her what a traitor she is and launches an attack on Athens, where Zeus assisted him in his quest and granted him the request he made. By accomplishing so, Athens was supposed to provide the monster, which lived in the labyrinth beneath their palace, Knossos, approximately seven young men and women each year as offerings. Beginning with an account of the conditions on Crete, Saint utilised those details to her advantage, using them as a precursor to Ariadne's potential fate in addition to a first indication of what would happen to the women in the course of the novel. This is crucial to take into account when looking at the next plot sections because, as can be recognised, Saint used the parallels between the epics, the past, and the present to her advantage in order to steer the original myth in the right direction throughout the entirety of the novel.

To clarify further, it's important to delve into the specifics of the world setting, as the monster that Minos utilises to subjugate Athens is Ariadne's sibling—the Minotaur. Early in the narrative, the heroine tells the tale of how the Minotaur came to be. She tells how King Minos, like any conceited hero who gains authority, attempted to trick Poseidon by offering a regular bull in place of the sacred bull that the sea god, Poseidon, had instructed him to sacrifice. Consequently, in his wrath, Poseidon afflicts Minos' wife, Pasiphae with lust for the bull. In order to dupe the bull into mounting her, she seeks the help of Daedalus, the inventor of the palace, to build a lifelike wooden cow that she might conceal within and give birth to the animal's child—the Minotaur. By

doing so, Minos' pride becomes injured, and Ariadne's family is scandalised and falls into humiliation:

He did not level his sleek, silver vengeance directly at Minos, the man who had sought to betray him and dishonour him, but turned instead upon my mother, the Queen of Crete, and riled her to insanity with passion for the bull. Incensed with an animalistic lust, the desire made her conniving and clever and she persuaded the unsuspecting Daedalus to create a wooden cow so convincing that the bull was fooled into mounting both it and the maddened queen, hidden within. (p.16)

Here, Saint purposefully reveals the details of the Minotaur's creation to illustrate how women are viewed as a source of humiliation for men. Women are frequently the targets of these punishments, and the author makes use of this particular idea as a recurring theme throughout the course of her work. Saint's voyage may readily fit into patriarchal ideas about women. Putting it simply, considering men profess to be their "owners," women are viewed as valuable commodities, and harming them is perceived as both an act of power and an insult to their dignity:

Poseidon, whilst seeming to miss his target, had struck with deadly accuracy. Leaving Minos untouched but disgracing his wife in so grotesque a fashion humbled the man – cuckolded by a dumb beast and wedded to a woman frenzied with unnatural desires. Pasiphae was beautiful and her divine heritage had made her a magnificent prize to Minos in marriage. It was her very delicacy, her refinement and her sweetness that had made her his boast and must have made her degradation seem so very delectable to Poseidon. If you had anything that made you proud, that elevated you above your mortal fellows, it seemed to me that the gods would find delight in smashing it to smithereens. (p.20)

As the sequence develops, Ariadne describes her growing fears as a child, of becoming the next victim of a man's wrongs. It is vital to consider the manner in which Saint showcases her character in her childhood, training her mind and pondering on the positions of power she was between. The heroine, as a female princess, demonstrates the mindset in which she is trained to have as a female child. This is observed through her reaction to her mother's tragedy, instead of grieving for her mother, Saint allows us to witness her growing fears of how that could be possibly her fate one day:

I began to weep; fearfully regarding each golden curl as bait to those divine colossi that strode the heavens and could snatch up our tiny triumphs and rub them into dust between their immortal fingers. My handmaiden, Eirene, found me sobbing into a bemused Phaedra's hair. 'Ariadne,' she crooned. She must have pitied me and the particularly grotesque way in which the innocence of my childhood had been so shaken. 'What's the matter?' No doubt she thought I cried for my mother's shame, but I had a child's self-absorption and I was worried now for me. 'What if the gods—' I gulped through my tears. 'What if they take my hair and leave me bald and ugly?' (p.20)

In keeping with both Rubin Gayle's thesis on social structure and Beauvoir's idea on the division of the two sexes, Saint approaches the original myth by closely examining the environment surrounding Ariadne. By doing this, she weaves a new

perspective onto the original myth by highlighting the gender system imposed on the female characters from the very beginning. Saint illustrates the clear gap and the gendered modes of both the male and female characters, illustrating the dehumanisation and devaluation of women in classical literature. Furthermore, demonstrating how they are still held up as representations of men's honour and authority in many countries, according to numerous traditional and cultural beliefs. This reflects Rubin's argument that humanity imposed "a systematic social apparatus which takes up females as raw materials and fashions domesticated women as products" (1975). Moreover, Saint does not overlook the way that women's devaluation instantly renders them worthless as tradeable commodities; this is seen in the exchange between Ariadne and her sister. When Phaedra asserts that "princesses cannot be bald." It is important to take into account how the author employs language in this instance. Through the use of the word "cannot," the author highlights the role that Ariadne was forced to play and the fact that there was no other option available. Ariadne appears to be mulling over her sister's remarks shortly thereafter; her inner monologue reveals her anxiety about failing to carry out her duties as well as the realisation that she would be seen as worthless and untradeable if she is made to feel degraded:

A bald princess would be useless. Minos had always spoken of the marriage I would make one day; a glorious union that would heap honour upon Crete. He should not have boasted. The creeping realisation chilled my bones. How could I defend myself against his wrongdoing? If the gods were offended by him and struck down his wife, then why not his daughter. (p.21)

In this instance Saint lays the groundwork for her premise by foreshadowing the consequences and hazards that women experience on a daily basis simply because they are the other/sub gender. In this regard, Ariadne, as a character, subconsciously becomes aware of her limited power and the confinements she is subjected to as a princess for she states: "What I did not know was that I had hit upon a truth of womanhood: however blameless a life we led, the passions and the greed of men could bring us to ruin, and there was nothing we could do" (p.22). In the later scenes, Ariadne's conscious waking plays a crucial role in her evolution since, as the story progresses, her awareness acts as a catalyst for new developments.

Likewise, Saint embodies the mythological tales of other women or female goddesses in order to demonstrate the positions of power in the patriarchal system imposed on them, as well as a motif and a foreshadowing of the upcoming sequences.

This is shown multiple times with the stories of Medusa and Artemis. When Ariadne learns of Medusa's tale, she becomes aware of the extent women experience tragedy for their vulnerability. This is specifically demonstrated in the way Athena punishes Medusa for being raped. It is important to note that women often experience victim blaming for being harassed to this day. This goes hand in hand with Cahil's thesis on sexual harassment (2010), as indicated in the analysis of Circe, women are often pre victims of men's lust, and they often inflict their hate and self-blame towards themselves. In this regard, Athena's anger towards her priestess, Medusa, is a big indicator of how women often get the blame and the punishment for being vulnerable in these circumstances:

'Athena was angry,' Eirene went on. 'A virgin goddess, she could not stand for such a brazen crime in her own temple. She must punish the girl who was so shameless as to be overpowered by Poseidon and to offend Athena's sight so vilely with her undoing' (p.23)

It is noteworthy to recognise how Ariadne was conditioned as a young girl to accept the constraints placed on her gender; the more she was taught about the difficulties faced by these women, the more she was expected to accept her place in the patriarchal system. However, Ariadne is at this point unable to comprehend the reasoning behind Athena's deed; it seemed hardly appropriate for a woman to suffer the consequences of a male god's acts. With that in mind, the heroine comprehends completely the larger picture of the gendered system she is subjugated to and becomes conscious of the restrictions and confines of her position:

Medusa had to pay for Poseidon's act. It made no sense at all, and then I tilted my head and saw it with the logic of the gods. The pieces slid into place: a terrible picture when viewed from our mortal perspective, like the beauty of a spider's web that must look so horrifying to the fly. (p.23)

Additionally, Saint draws parallels between the stories of Medusa and her mother, Pasiphae, through the inner monologue of her character. This is vital to take into account because the story describes how Pasiphae shrinks and breaks apart as a result of the humiliation and suffering she endured. As a witness to her mother's fall, Ariadne conveys the entire picture of her agony, illustrating how her mother lost her voice, her will, and her power. Through Ariadne, Saint explores the manner in which Pasiphae was mostly silenced; although the character presents her mother from a child's point of view, it is highly detailed and demonstrates the dehumanisation to which she

was subjected. The terminology is purposefully used by the author to accomplish this. Ariadne, for example, tells of how her mother “withdrew to an unreachable corner of her sound” becoming a “thin shell lying almost transparent on the sand, worn to nearly nothing by the crashing waves”. In this section Saint adopts a very delicate perpendicular to highlight how Pasiphae was portrayed as "damaged" and "useless," as well as her helplessness and devaluation as a woman and queen. Saint also makes little effort to emphasise the innocence of her character when she was younger. As Ariadne saw her mother, she was unable to fathom how her mother had come to be in that situation or the positions of authority that women were forced into fully:

I would be Medusa, if it came to it, I resolved. If the gods held me accountable one day for the sins of someone else, if they came for me to punish a man's actions, I would not hide away like Pasiphae. I would wear that coronet of snakes and the world would shrink from me instead. (p.23)

Saint further, demonstrates the relevance of the Minotaur as a representation of her mother's demise and her rage as a witness. She is tasked with caring for her half-brother as he grows, along with her mother. This seems to be a significant course of action since it displays Ariadne's empathy and exasperation. As the monster gets bigger, the heroine, who is now a teenager, finds herself desiring that her brother will someday grow up and resisting the way he is shaped to mirror both her father's avarice and her mother's tragedy. Nevertheless, the monster escapes control and is kept in check by Daedalus' labyrinth beneath their palace, where it feasts annually on fourteen youngsters from Athens:

– A slowly boiling anger – that I could not bring myself to end him while I still could. To smash a brick down on his head as he ate, to jam a spear into the vulnerable human flesh at his side – even as a girl, I suppose I could have done it whilst he was still a calf. But I could not bring myself to do it, and by the time I had truly grasped what he was – and what use Minos would have for him when he grasped it, too – he was well beyond my strength. (p.23)

Saint also portrays a society where women's reputations are often trampled upon, but males are treated with a different standard. An example would be the way Minos exploits the monster as a weapon in his advantage and even goes so far as to refer to him as his "son," showing how men's conceit and desire for dominance and power are unfathomable and frequently come at the expense of women's battles. Ariadne, particularly translates how Minos' outlook on the monster shifted after he discovered how he might utilise him:

Our son? I wondered, not yet understanding what he meant. I slowly perceived, in my incredulity, that it was pride warming the stern angles of his face. He was proud of the

monster we had nurtured in the heart of the palace, proud of the reputation it had won him. Far from bringing ridicule upon the cuckolded Minos' head, Poseidon had delivered him a fearsome weapon, a divine brute that Minos had come to see would only strengthen his status-- mother's private constellation of shame intermingled with love and despair no longer; instead, he became my father's display of dominance to the world. I saw why he proclaimed him the Minotaur, stamping this divine monstrosity with his own name and aligning its legendary status with his own from its very birth. (p.30)

Furthermore, the protagonist of the work vividly depicts the fury she observed enveloping her mother's face as she saw her harbouring resentment and humiliation and how she is easily manipulated, oblivious to her pain. Saint goes on to illustrate Pasiphae's consequences. She lost her voice and her power in addition to her honour. This is illustrated by the author's use of the terms "mute" and "motionless" to characterise her. Saint portrays the way in which her character is completely devalued and dehumanised as a result of a man's behaviour, while having less "life" than a statue. This is important due to how it highlights the systemic gender classism that places women at the base of the pyramid and devalues them according to their gender and sex.

Additionally, as the scene progresses, Ariadne addresses the conditions in the city and her life as a princess; it is clear from her portrayal that Minos, as a ruler, uses the monster to establish his power while putting his people's fear of him to shield himself. In this sense, Saint leverages Minos to depict the toxicity of masculine authority and pride by displaying a typical heroic classical figure from the perspective of those under his authority. This may be considered as a perfect picture of how men weaponize the power they are offered on a hierarchical scale. This is demonstrated not only from Ariadne's point of view but also by displaying how the show of dominance affects everyone in her immediate vicinity:

I was a girl, you see, of just eighteen and lucky to still be able to call myself such. I had led a sheltered life, veiled and hidden behind high walls. I was lucky that my father kept me as a prize he had yet to bestow; that he hadn't traded me for a foreign alliance, bundling me on a ship bound for distant shores to spread his influence afar, sold like a dumb beast at market. But that was all about to change. (p.35)

It is pertinent to recognise how Ariadne is presented when her father offers her as "goods" to be traded given that Saint illustrates the extent to which women may be objectified. This comes in accordance with Rubin's analysis of how women are used by tradesmen as sexual props to gratify the lusts of the opposite sex or gender:

Women are given in marriage, taken in battle, exchanged for favors, sent as tribute, traded, bought, and sold. Far from being confined to the "primitive" world, these practices seem only to become more pronounced and commercialized in more "civilized" societies(...)And if men

have been sexual subjects—exchangers—and women sexual semi-objects—gifts— (Rubin. 1975, p.75)

Here, Ariadne was portrayed almost exactly as an item would be shown to a customer. As she communicates that she is there. The suitor of whom she was offered examines her from head to toe as if perceiving an object, Ariadne's perspective in this scene highly details an uncomfortable image of how dehumanised the character was:

Cinyras of Cyprus was so close to me I could feel his breath on my face. Resolutely, I turned my eyes away but he took my chin between his fingers and angled my face back towards him. In the dim room, his eyes flashed black. Dark curls clustered over his head. His lips shone wetly, inches from mine. I fought the urge to step away from the reek of his breath in my mouth, to lift up my skirts and run from the room. Whilst Minos smiled approvingly, I had to stand still, so I rooted my feet to the floor and gazed ahead. To my relief, he retreated a couple of paces. 'She is as lovely as you said,' he commented. (p.40)

After this scene, Saint shows Ariadne's helplessness as she understands her fate; instead of desiring to accept her role, she conveys a sense of powerlessness and desperation as well as an internal rejection to the notion of being "sold." Her character exhibits a significant initial development in this sense as she begins to gravitate more towards her own will than her forced role. Furthermore, it is noted that Ariadne exhibits resistance and makes an effort to speak up as she is approached and touched by Cinyras: "I ground my teeth, swallowed my humiliation, tried to shift away, though it only made his fingers clamp more tightly" (p.262).

Furthermore, when Theseus shows up as one of the sacrifices presented to feed the monster that laid beneath their palace, both Ariadne and her little sister are drawn to him, as he was the prince of Athens, who has volunteered as a sacrifice. Both characters find themselves besotted towards him. Ariadne finds herself giving him her life as well as her sister when she tries to assist him in killing her brother/monster. As previously mentioned, Saint makes frequent comparisons between her characters and classic stories. As a result, Ariadne, however unknowingly, suffers a destiny akin to that of Minos and the way he punished Scylla in the epic. This is vital to note as female characters were often utilised as devices to buffer the heroic figures in mythologies. Therefore, when Ariadne seeks a way to help Theseus kill the monster, she embodies the same fate as Scylla, by betraying her family. Saint navigates the way in which Ariadne helps her hero, by showcasing him as her key to freedom yet another thread that would eventually tie her up as a victim of his heroic acts. Nevertheless, when Theseus promised to help her and her sister and that he would wed her, Ariadne unintentionally

imprisoned herself in the same exact box she was already in, entrusting her fate to a man:

Our plans were made. I knew I should be wracked with doubt but I knew that I would do this. Betray my father. Send death to my brother, wrapped in a red cord that would bring his killer back to me. Desert my mother. And, of course, leave Crete and never return. I will not say it was an easy decision but it was the only one I could have made. The world was on fire and Theseus was a shaded, green pool. (p.88)

When Theseus, as a heroic male character, defeats the Minotaur and helps all the hostages out unharmed, Ariadne finds hope in her escape with him. It is crucial to consider that while Ariadne as a character, was naive to her position as a woman, she had also seen Theseus not only as a potential lover but also as her way out of the gender binary structure of her environment:

I was a fitting wife for a legendary hero and I would prove it. My story would not be one of death and suffering and sacrifice. I would take my own place in the songs that would be sung about Theseus: the princess who saved him and ended the monstrosity that blighted Crete. (p.91)

As Theseus leaves her sister behind, and they sail to the deserted island of Naxos however, Adriane's mindset shifts into a slow realisation of her position both as a woman and the parallelism of her action to those women before her:

Except that the Minotaur was dead. And I stood now on an enemy ship, a lone woman amongst strange men, a woman lost to her home forever. No guards would pursue me to defend my honour. If anyone came for me, it would be to exact a terrible revenge. I thought of Scylla, drowning. (p.102)

Similar to Miller's portrayal of Circe, Saint here illustrates the subconscious awareness that Ariadne began to acquire when she was stripped of her shield as a princess. Ariadne learns of the dangers that she faces as a "free" woman because she was not only vulnerable as obtainable goods but also lacked bodily protection. Here, the author not only demonstrates Ariadne's ignorance that caused her to flee her island, but also how her training to be helpless as the inferior gender left her lacking a survival instinct. In this way, Saint portrays the desperation and constraints associated with her character's life as a woman by employing the original course of action from the original narrative. Therefore, when they reach the island of Naxos, and Theseus turns her to 'damaged goods' as a prize to his quest as a hero, he abandons her in the island, tasting the exact fate of those women she was once told of:

“I had given Theseus the clue to the Labyrinth: fourteen lives of Athens and the death of my own brother. In exchange, he granted me perhaps a week to live in exile, imprisoned on a desolate island” (p.112).

Consequently, Ariadne's life in Crete demonstrates the way she was born into a society that regarded her as a potential victim of men's actions and as a woman bound by her gender. Nonetheless, A shift occurred in her subconsciousness as a result of her realisation of her situation and her mother's tragedy. Because she will always be an object first and foremost, there to appease male characters, her initial rebellion and attempt to escape with Theseus thus highlight the limitations she was subjected to in the societal structures.

3.2. The Isolation of Ariadne: The De-enactment of Gender

Saint employs Ariadne's isolation as an instrument for attempting to get her character to transform; the author translates a thorough account of her heroine's early years on the island and employs it as a plot point to highlight the character's eventual act of independence and defiance of the gendered system she was raised in. To further explain, this is important to consider as it reflects not only Ariadne's naivety but also the fashion in which she trained her mind to believe she is powerless without any male figure shielding her. Thus, with the revelation that Ariadne was abandoned. The character renders herself as useless in her mind for she did not even consider that there are chances to survive. Saint uses her character's inner monologue to illustrate this point: “he granted me perhaps a week to live in exile, imprisoned on a desolate island”. Beauvoir's central argument in *The Second Sex* is reinforced by Saint's depiction of how males essentially oppress women as the "Other" on all fronts and in opposition to men. Ariadne appears to have been socialised to believe that she has less capabilities and values the moment she was abandoned. In accordance, Beauvoir's thesis delves deeper into the idea that women are innately immanent and inward, while men are meant to create, invent, and rule, and women are meant to wait for, depend on, and be saved by men. This distinction between the sexes is a key component of Beauvoir's dissertation (1949). Therefore, it is important to consider how Ariadne responded to her abandonment. Despite the fact that Theseus had abandoned her, she nevertheless felt powerless to act on her own initiative and became desperate for his return. Given that

she was trained to do so, the character thus exhibits traits of the typical othered gender role:

There was nowhere to go, but I could not stay in that bed a second longer. Consumed with a restless energy, I dressed frantically – no choice but to put my bronze dress back on, as that was all I had. A strange choice for a prisoner, an exile, whatever I was now – not a princess, not a collaborator or co-conspirator, not a wife. My movements were jerky, uncontrolled, my fingers clumsy. I snapped my head around at the slightest movement, not sure whether to panic or rejoice when my mind tricked me into thinking I heard the sound of another person. These delusions would plague me in the lonely days and nights to come. As my mind unravelled, I would hear footsteps on the stairs and my heart would seize with joy that Theseus had returned, then with terror that it was a brigand or a pirate or a desperate sailor wrecked upon the shore and coming for me. (p.116)

Indeed, this initial stage of the sequence in fact offers a significant insight on how one is trained to be a certain gender—a lady in this case—rather than becoming individuals; this is particularly relevant in light of the Otherness that is placed on "women." Saint thus presents an unmistakably vivid picture of how Ariadne's naivete and excessive reliance on men are more deeply ingrained in the way that she was taught to submit; as a result, her actions are more subconscious as an outcome of her mental imprisonment. Furthermore, as the aforementioned quotation highlights, Ariadne minimises her identity to being "nothing" and not even a "wife," illuminating the ways in which women were socialised to view themselves as inferior. In her absence from her "husband," Theseus, she feels deformed, imperfect, and worthless. It is clear from the character's initial disorientation and mental state that being othered as a subgenre has its effects. The heroine herself is proof of how her thinking was structured to adhere to particular norms, which prevented her from going beyond the boundaries imposed upon her. Therefore, when Ariadne becomes abandoned, she lacks the confidence in her own capabilities and the guts to explore the island. At first, she follows the paths taken by other women, including her mother and the stories that paralleled with her mother's fate, and submits to her fate rather than resisting it:

My days were spent in desultory walking. I did not dare to explore the island further. I walked the beach, I walked the cliffs and I scanned the flat expanse of the sea, hour upon hour. It remained empty.- I considered, with a strange sense of calm, ending it all more quickly. -I was afraid and more pathetically, I still clung to that tiny crumb of hope. I hoped against all hope that Theseus would take pity on me, that he would relent, that he might return and I could be saved. (p.117)

Saint likewise skilfully converts Ariadne's anger from her despair. This is a crucial turn of events for the retelling since it reminds Ariadne of her limitations and

her destiny as a woman, while also highlighting the significant rage that women suppress inside. Consequently, when Ariadne becomes enraged and recognises how she was deceived, she simultaneously manages to break free from the restraints on her voice and finds herself yelling in defiance:

You would be dead if it wasn't for me!' I screamed at Theseus across the cliffs, over the indifferent ocean. 'Your flesh would be rotting off your bones in the Labyrinth if I had not saved you! You are no hero, you faithless coward!'. (p.119)

Saint utilises Ariadne's frustration as a catalyst to free her subconscious mind from its bonds, allowing her to both stray from the "naivety" of her mindset and act as a provocation that would ultimately lead to her survival on the land. As an outcome, this sequence heavily suggests the manner in which the character begins to de-enact her gender. Notwithstanding the aspects of gender that are assigned to women and men, the subversion of gender is not limited to the act of becoming wholly unfit for a woman; rather, it can be argued that the act of reshaping one's identity through resistance to roles that are placed upon it constitutes a gender-bending act in and of itself. Thus, Saint gradually undoes the way her character's subconscious seeks for a masculine figure to complete her when she grants Ariadne a voice to express her frustration. Ariadne purposefully exploited her awakening into her source of survival motivation. By expressing how her perspective on the island has changed, the heroine exemplifies this:

The ocean had always been a friend to me, back in Crete. The sight of it would always soothe my soul. Since Theseus' desertion, it had been a taunting enemy, staying so resolutely empty as I willed it desperately to summon back his ship and return him to me. But today, it would be a friend again. I would sit on the warm sand and watch the white-crested waves sparkle. (p.130)

It is noted that Ariadne does not only accept the reality when it downed her, but she also resisted and refused to give up her remaining days. In doing so, the character's drive reflects her will to resist despite the lack of sources or life on the island, this is vital to navigate as the character does not submit to her limitations, withstanding the little chance of survival she had. Indeed, this course of action symbolises her resistance to becoming nothing. Furthermore, as the tale progresses and Ariadne experiences the miracles of Dionysus, she repeatedly questions the motives behind the act of blessing. In contrast to her first demeanour, the character displays a more certain and mature attitude in the scene; as Dionysus sails closer to the island, Ariadne mulls over all the potential outcomes for her, both as a visitor and as a woman:

I drew back behind the rock, my heart pounding and thoughts racing. This island, which I had thought to be my lonely tomb, was now the destination of an unpredictable, unimaginably powerful Olympian god. If it occurred to him, he could strike me dead in an instant. Or worse. I had no defence; no means of protection. I had watched him transform men into dumb beasts of the sea. (p.153)

In addition, the author repeatedly highlights the similarities between Ariadne's acts and Medusa's as she continues with her observations. The heroine muses over the prospect of punishment for sharing Theseus's bed in the god's house. She accepts the possibility that she may suffer the same fate as Medusa as an outcome of Athena's wrath. The character therefore illustrates how this sequence may present another patriarchal stage that would end her life for a decision that she made with Theseus. Therefore, she feels herself confined in the same dread of experiencing that widely known fate of all the women she learned of:

I thought of Athena's fury at Medusa for her ravishment by Poseidon in her temple, and I quaked. I had gone willingly. Now, somewhere over that wide blue sea, Theseus lolled with impunity on royal couches, admired by all for his bravery, his noble and heroic exploits – and like a thousand women before me, I would pay the price of what we had done together. (p.153)

Nonetheless, as indicated previously, given the character's demeanour had already witnessed a shift, Ariadne does not employ the typical attitude of submitting. Instead, she finds herself shielding her mind with her rage towards the limited possibilities of survival for she was a woman, and her struggle was a trophy for men's arrogance. Thus, the character instead, embraces her rage and envisioned herself with Medusa's snakes crown, showcasing a fearless attitude that would instead, make those heroes cringe away:

I could die whimpering or I could face my fate with the courage of all those women before me. I held Medusa's image in my head, calming my deep ragged breaths. Her snakes hissed and spat and contorted about her head, striking fear into the hearts of so-called heroes as they cringed away. I could be the same. My rage would be my shield. Even though Dionysus could sizzle my flesh to nothing with a flash of his golden eyes, I would not cringe away in fear. (p.153)

Saint here, successfully showcases her character's development within the boundaries of the original tale while exploring the gender structure of the world settings without stripping her of her qualities. This is worth noting as Ariadne's femininity throughout the novel becomes her strength. While the character was completely isolated and outside the social gender and sex system. The character's embracement of her femininity does not make her weaker or less valuable, the character breaks out of the gendered norms by forging an unclassical picture of a heroine using her given

qualities both as a feminine character and as a 'woman' outside the gendered modes. Additionally, Saint does not only navigate the spectrum of gender using Ariadne, but also by weaponizing Dionysus' qualities as a fluid god. To elaborate, it is worth noting that by the physical appearance alone, Dionysus embodies both the feminine and masculine qualities that would be traditionally imposed on either gender:

His figure was slight and graceful as he strode through the surf. Behind him, the man looked lumpen and coarse, his heavily muscled arms swinging awkwardly and his skin rough and reddened. Dionysus looked as though he had only just reached manhood; his face was boyish, gleaming with barely repressed mischief and mirth. He betrayed no surprise at finding me here but looked warmly at me, as though he were approaching an old friend. (p.155)

The author subsequently continues to demonstrate how Dionysus interacts to Ariadne as an equal rather than just approaching her in a conventional way. The strongest indication of that may come from the terminology selections in the preceding quotation. Saint's utilisation of words here emphasises how Ariadne was given a voice rather than being expected to surrender. In this way, Dionysus overcomes the masculine "need" to dominate by approaching the heroine in an inviting manner. Despite the fact that Dionysus is an Olympian god with a realm so formidable that Ariadne could not have withstand, the god permits Ariadne to speak, defying the anticipated and predictable course of events portrayed in classical literature. Ariadne does not only get treated as equal, but more or less she is seen for her very being.

Throughout the encounter, Saint emphasises on the power Dionysus had as a male god, indicating the extent of which he breaks the gender norms. Dionysus shows both empathy towards Ariadne and converses with her as an equal in his stay, initially, the character sets herself in doubts for the obvious positions of power. However, Saint successfully manages to showcase a little yet a significant picture of the gender modes unarticulated in the sequence and the empowering effect it had on the heroine:

It was hard, though, to fear him so greatly. I knew that any chance offence I might give him, whether intended or not, could see me voiceless and bound in a thick, grey skin beneath the waves, but he was so engaging and kind that I could forget from minute to minute with whom I conversed. (p.158)

Furthermore, the author expertly crafts Dionysus' persona so that he embodies both empathy and masculinity without resorting to force or, more accurately, exerting his dominance. Instead, he offers Ariadne the duty of island guardian and allows her to break free from the constraints of her gender. As a result, Ariadne finds herself entirely dependent on her own abilities and gradually transforms her sense of self. This

approach humanises Ariadne while simultaneously detains her mind. The scene highlights Ariadne's value as an individual and not merely based on her given gender. Despite Dionysus's superior strength, his demeanour never fails to provide a perspective that transcends both of their gender binary. Likewise, the way Dionysus looks betrays the stereotypical view of a masculine man, reflecting a binary that is entirely outside of the gender norms that Ariadne was raised to.

Additionally, Saint's handling of Ariadne's developing intimacy to Dionysus suggests that both parties value one another. Therefore, although Ariadne values her femininity and does not submit to Dionysus as a lesser gender, she also does not devalue herself in his presence. In return, Dionysus places a great deal of importance on Ariadne, as evidenced by the infamous act in which he casts Ariadne's jewelled crown into the sky, giving birth to the constellation Corona Borealis:

'It can be stolen, it can be twisted or tarnished and lose its lustre,' he went on. 'I want no gift that I give to you to be so transient. And so I took it from your head, where it can only look dull in comparison to your radiance, and I put it somewhere it will shine forever.' He cupped my cheek in his hand and lifted my chin to the dark bowl of the night sky. 'See the new constellation there?' In the eternity of night, I saw the brand new pinpricks of light that shone in a sweeping arc. The lustre of my crown, now a fiery illumination against the darkness. (p.213)

The hypothesis put forward by Butler regarding the breaking of gender acts is being alluded to by this development; yet, in this instance, the act of breaking out of the gender label is more about the roles that are placed upon them and the binary framework than it is about the label itself. This is significant since gender transcends labels; hence, Dionysus's recognition of Ariadne as a being, without distinction, represents a subtly circumventing of the limitations:

We ate our meals together, and when he presided over the maenads' worship I found myself sitting at his side rather than kneeling with them. The days were strung together like beads on a cord – a beautiful necklace, a gift I had never expected. (p.209)

Ariadne's growing intimacy with Dionysus also appears to be entirely out of will and not obligation, which may not seem as significant given that he is in a position of power and can assume whatever he wishes. However, the character frees herself from the notion of submission and acts in accordance with her whole will. Hence, in addition to changing gender classism as Beauvoir would have defined it, this course of action embraces the aspects of both characters' respective genders and gives them access to opportunities that go beyond their binary and gender-restricted identities. To get into further detail, it's essential to gain insight into how Ariadne perceives

motherhood. The author highlights her character's ambition to become a mom as well as her wish to have children. This is an important plot point that Saint explores since, in addition to examining the spectrum of Ariadne's femininity at its peak, she also demonstrates the opposite when navigating her sister's perspective, which will be covered in the following section. In this sense, Ariadne does not feel compelled to give up her femininity or her ability to give birth.

Nevertheless, the novelist approaches Ariadne's pregnancy and birth in a delicate yet realistic way. Through her heroine, she depicts the struggle and suffering that comes with birth, similarly to Miller's exploration. Saint too sets a stage that demonstrates the position of women in a limited environment, displaying both their struggle and strength when giving birth. Ariadne too, makes it evident when she expresses her fears and tells the tales she's heard of women giving birth. The idea of motherhood, while weaponised against women to control them, is possibly one of the biggest hardships a being can undergo. Therefore, Saint translates the significance of birth and motherhood on the positive spectrum through Ariadne, to showcase her character's strength and more importantly without nerving her personality. Indeed, the author instead utilises Ariadne's experience as an empowering image that is meant to document the experiences of women, instead of alternating them:

Who knew how many women, right at that moment, were struggling to do as I did? All of us straining and grunting to bear our babies to safety. I pictured them in my mind as each wave squeezed my belly. Instead of floundering, I tried to ride each wave to its end and catch my breath in the moments of quiet between. I saw the women of the world – on wide, soft couches in golden palaces, in shaded tents on desert sands, in huts built of mud or stone, in lands that ranged to the ends of the earth – and as I braced upon my hands and knees, I felt that we surged in synchrony with one another. Like a vast constellation of stars pinpricking the night sky, I could feel us all strive together to each bring new sparks of light into the universe. I thought I could feel their support, their hands upon my back. (p.215)

Furthermore, as Ariadne lives her life content, the heroine discovers that her husband sets up rituals involving sacrificing animals that he'd bring back to life, initially, she is horrified by the discovery and finds herself unable to confront Dionysus, the heroine, here displays discontent in having to confront him:

How had I become uncertain of my right to walk upon the hills of my own island, where I ruled beside a god? Why did I sneak so stealthily through the trees, rather than striding confidently to my place at my own husband's side? (p.276)

Saint demonstrates Ariadne's confusion in this scene, as she is indecisive as to which part of her to adapt to confront the situation; in this regard, the character showcases the traces of how she found herself alluded to be content in her role as a

mother and a wife, but also the shift in how she once finally saw herself on an equal footing as the man she married. When the heroine eventually confronts Dionysus and interacts with his followers, she realises the significance and symbolism in his actions, while immoral, his female followers seemed to be all victims of male dominance and sins. This is shown through her conversation with one of the maidens, when she details the loss of her daughter for being a girl, rather than a boy:

“A girl,” he said, “what am I to do with a girl? Cast it out upon a hillside, it is nothing but a pointless mouth to feed.” Her face twisted. ‘They tore her from my arms even when I screamed. She cried and I screamed but they carried her away and I screamed more until the world went black around me. I did not wake for days and my baby was long dead on an empty hillside by then, but I heard her crying wherever I went, whatever I did. The crying only quieted when I climbed aboard that boat and came to Naxos. I pulled the oars myself, every stroke. When I reached this shore, it was the first happiness I had known, except for that one perfect moment when I held my child. I smiled so much I thought that my face would break in two. (p.283)

It is crucial to comprehend the cultural and traditional resonance of this sequence. Saint exploits the widespread notion that girls are typically devalued in various societies. For example, many Eastern societies still cling to the belief that having a male child will validate their lineage, heritage, and dignity. In addition, the author shows a change in Dionysus' persona as a masculine god in order to highlight both his strengths and his conceit. When Dionysus challenges his brother, the heroine observes that he is much like other men who feed off of pride and power:

I had fallen in love with his vulnerability all those years ago. I had thought it made him different to all other men and gods alike. But it was his misery that made me so uneasy now. Because if I had learned anything, I had learned enough to know that a god in pain is dangerous. (p.319)

Nevertheless, when Dionysus's conceit gets the better of him, Ariadne sees the destiny she had previously feared coming to pass. As Dionysus changes the women's thoughts on his brother's island, the character displays fear and dread. The heroine then comes to the realisation that men would constantly target them in an effort to undermine each other's self-worth. As the conflict progresses, Dionysus kills the island's children and is unable to bring them back to life, making Ariadne and all the other women and mothers around her victims of his transgressions. In this way, Saint illustrates how individuals in positions of authority frequently prey on the weakest to showcase their control; in this instance, the women and children ended up as the victims of these acts of violence:

I looked at the frightened women clustered around me. They had come to Dionysus, to Naxos, for sanctuary. For a life of peace, away from those who sought to make their lives miserable

and tormented. This is not what they had come to us for. In my breast, I felt a molten anger towards my husband. He had kept us sobbing in fear of him in the darkness of the ship whilst he played his hideous games with the Argive women. They had done nothing to him but refuse him. (p.323)

Thus, when Ariadne witnesses the tragedy bestowed on these women, her character fully realises the reality of how those women before her, the mothers in front of her, and all these victims were seen as justifiable objects paid for men's actions:

Pasiphae. Semele. Medusa. Now a hundred grieving mothers. The price we paid for the resentment, the lust and the greed of arrogant men was our pain, shining and bright like the blade of a newly honed knife. Dionysus had once seemed to me the best of them all, but I saw him now for what he was, no different from the mightiest of the gods. Or the basest of men. (p.326)

In the last sequence, Saint presents Ariadne's character breaking from her submission and domesticated identity. In the wake of Dionysus' actions, the heroine displays a final act of resistance, she refuses to submit to her fate as a given fact, but rather finds herself unable to accept the idea of being responsible for a man's arrogance:

The fragile peace of Naxos had held because I told myself that my husband offered the wronged women of the world a sanctuary and an outlet for their pain. But he had surpassed his lightning-wielding father and his earth-shaking uncle at long last: even they had never broken so many women in one fell swoop. In terms of heartbreak, Dionysus could call himself the greatest of all the gods now. He could measure his glory in female torment and blaze his legend across the heavens as the conqueror of infants, destroyer of the innocent. (p.327)

Thus, as the last scene unfolds, Saint illustrates her heroine's final breaking of identity, even though she had not been able to live a life out of her gender role completely, the character's wilfulness in the last act. While tragic, demonstrates and translates an empowering finale, for when Ariadne tries to stop the madness and falls a victim amidst the clashing, her final act depicts a courageous, non-regrettable act that illustrates her transformation as a struggling human amidst societal mould that subjected her to be a victim just like her sister, and the other goddesses and women.

Consequently, the narrative does not directly provide a happy ending or a remedy for women. By imposing "male" traits (in this case, the general capabilities of being) on the characters' personalities, it delicately highlights the range of hardships and does not discount the experience a woman goes through to free herself from her constraints. The pursuit of equality in this sense does not equate to conceit, haughtiness, or the need to be emotionally cold. Rather, her focus is on demonstrating how the concept of womanhood is designed to marginalise and dehumanise women. That being said, this

does not imply that a woman must give up her empathy, embrace her femininity, or reject all males in order to be free from the socially imposed gender norms.

3.3. Phaedra: The Silenced Voice of Athens

This section is meant to navigate the way Saint also shows the opposite extreme of the feminine spectrum in her portrayal of Ariadne's sister's struggle, Pheadra; for the character had a masculine attitude and was not content with being a lady as shown from her perspective. She too battled for power after being sold for her father's transgressions. Saint demonstrates throughout the narrative her battle with parenthood, her love for her kids, and her fervent desire for independence—even if it meant relying on a man who seemed to behave abnormally in terms of his gender. Saint illustrates how her tragedy was contained inside the limitations of her kingdom and the authority bestowed upon her, with suicide appearing to be the only way out.

Saint offers Pheadra's perspective right after Ariadne's departure from their island. In the initial chapters Pheadra is presented as a childish girl that acted recklessly. However, when the author offers her perspective, Pheadra's character seems to come with unique qualities that are not exactly fitting to her gender role. This is deliberately shown as Pheadra comes to the realisation that Theseus had sailed with her sister without her. The character does not only show immediate anger, but she regrets how she submitted to her position of power and dependent on Theseus instead:

“A terrible suspicion was swelling inside of me, and I was beginning to wish I had taken Theseus' club and smashed the creature's skull to pieces myself, rather than waiting for him to do it for us” (p.126).

Furthermore, Pheadra does not fail to voice the questions one would ponder on in regards of her sister; when her brother informs her of her sister's 'death' according to Theseus' claim, she immediately rejects the news by questioning her sister's death circumstances, the character elaborates on how it did not make any sense that Ariadne was the only one who'd be punished, when her actions were committed with the aid of Theseus. Nonetheless, Phaedra as a girl, was constantly shut down for questioning. Her brother, instead, does not question the gods or Theseus' words, but rather takes them as a matter of fact. Saint showcases the position of Phaedra in this scene, specifically, in

terms of the manner in which she is not heard or taken into consideration when raising questions, deeming her voiceless.

In an effort to strengthen relationships between the two cities, her brother Deucalion even goes so far as to arrange for her to be transferred in exchange for the king of Athens. At first, this conduct may seem fair, but Saint exploits language to illustrate that Phaedra is not only being used and exchanged as a commodity, but that she is also bearing the burdens of these men's conflicts, as Deucalion's remarks make clear:

The price is not paid yet, Phaedra.' — 'Minos is gone and no one knows when he will be back. We have no Minotaur. Whispers of rebellion surge around Knossos. We cannot afford the enmity of Athens now, but we have taken their children twice over and fed them alive to our monster. If Theseus had not killed it, we would have taken their Prince as well and it would stretch on forever; an endless sacrifice that we demanded of them. Their friendship will not be easy to come by' (p.139)

This sequence shows that Phaedra is not only made to pay for the indiscretions of other men, but that she also loses all control and is reduced to nothing more than an object devoid of agency. Saint traverses the same material that Gayle asserted to be true in her 1975 paper, *Traffic in Women*: "Women are given in marriage, taken in battle, exchanged for favours(...), sent as tribute, traded, bought, and sold". It is also worth noting that Phaedra, despite being a girl in her teen years, she was fully aware of how she was being utilised and how her fate as a woman makes her a victim just like those Saint used earlier in the retelling as a foreshadowing and symbol of the circular shared experiences and fates:

Deucalion spoke as though it were a gesture of unity between Athens and Crete, but I would be a hostage to the fragile peace he sought. I backed away from my brother, hand clasped to my mouth. I had thought he brought salvation with him. Instead he had traded my existing bondage for another. (p.141)

In contrast to her sister Ariadne, Saint uses Phaedra's character and growth as a weapon in an excessive manner as the recounting goes on. To further explain, it's critical to recognise that Phaedra has a more assertive attitude and is determined to overcome the social norms that would otherwise classify her as a sub gendered individual. Prior to Ariadne's isolation, Phaedra was always vocal and thought-provoking, unlike her sister. This is evident in the way she interacts with Theseus and, when necessary, attempts to adopt a role that does not correspond with her "gender":

‘Phaedra,’ he said to her, a hint of warmth and humour in his voice now. No icy glare for her. ‘You amaze me with your boldness. Already, you have achieved great feats that belie your age and your sex’ (p.84).

Ultimately, because of the environmental confinement she experiences, Phaedra's character regresses despite her robust demeanour. As a character, Phaedra deals directly with the societal ideas that the male figures in her life have forced upon her, in contrast to Ariadne. This becomes especially noteworthy after she sets sail for Athens. When Phaedra first arrives in Athens, she observes how Theseus, like any other hero, flaunted his conceit by telling mixed-up tales. In contrast to Ariadne, Phaedra was able to comprehend her predicament with clarity owing to her awareness. For instance, when Theseus boasts his exploits and heroic acts by killing the monster, he forbids Phaedra of speaking of her part in the quest, Saint interestingly notes the undermining of both the sisters’ roles in the heroic sequence indicating how women are often exploit and not noted for equally big achievements:

I wanted to make him say it – the killing of the Minotaur, the saving of the hostages that both Ariadne and I had played a vital role in. Who had restored his precious club to him? And now he wanted me to pretend it was all his doing; another story. (p.168)

Throughout the course of the novel, Phaedra's attempts to escape her status as a prize and a captive were only greeted with setbacks and further hardships. The character's experiences caused her to have extreme opinions about the male figures in her life as well as the circumstances surrounding them. This scenario includes some of the most significant moments in Phaedra's life, starting with her relationship that was devoid of love. As Phaedra eventually marries Theseus, she fails to adapt to her life as his wife nor is she able to grow fond of him:

“Our wedding day, like the birth of the Minotaur, was a memory I did not allow. Whenever it flickered in my mind (...) Athenian hands, kindly enough but strange and distant, twisted my hair into braids and draped me in flowing fabrics” (p.174).

Furthermore, the character constantly depicts how she gets overshadowed by her husband, simply for being a woman. This is deliberately demonstrated when they hold a successful festival that was entirely her idea, Saint showcases how Phaedra was both aware of her position of power and how men thrived on exploiting their success:

“I saw him grin, delighting in the adoration and the success. Although I knew the idea had come from me, I did not resent him taking the credit. It was satisfaction enough for me to see what I had achieved” (p.192).

The author conveys that through the heroine's words that Phaedra finds herself protecting her life with the false sensation of strength that Theseus granted her. As the heroine uses every strategy to survive in her immediate environment, Beauvoir's statements from 1949— “...counselling man to treat her as a slave while persuading her that she is a queen”—must be adhered to in this case. By doing so, she trains herself to believe that she was given a good life. Nonetheless, this illusion soon shatters when Phaedra finds out her sister is alive while pregnant. When she hears of the truth, her attempts to love Theseus and believe his lies get rendered as failed attempts. Which deemed her to realise that she was manipulated and fooled by the illusion that she built for herself for survival. The character here witnesses a shift not only in terms of identity but a regression in her maturity as she finds herself rejecting her womanhood in an extreme fashion. The author explores this through her pregnancy and birth. Unlike Ariadne, Phaedra does not only struggle to give birth, but she fails to connect to her motherly instincts:

He was not comforted by my inexpert cradling. I wept with frustration as he turned his head from my breast and howled. I remembered how my own mother had found it in herself to love a monster and I wondered why all I could feel was despair mixed with a faint pity for this tiny, angry baby who seemed so very disappointed to find himself with me. (p.223)

The author examines the lengths at which Phaedra found herself unable to commit to her motherly instincts. The character's guilt drenched her mind entirely, this is a severely important point as Phaedra's experience is connected to many experiences of women who underwent childbirth. The character falls into depression post her birth and is unable to commit to her role as a mother:

The truth was, I hated motherhood. From that first stunned moment after the birth, and every hour that followed. All day, the baby was clamped to my breast, greedy and desperate. All night, he seemed to cry, his piercing shriek destroying my peace, over and over again, until I thought I would lose my mind. Anxious that none should detect the horrifying lack of love, this strange abnormality that festered rotten and raw within me, I insisted that I was the one to tend to all of his needs. I sent my handmaidens away; I turned my face from the worried elder women, who seemed to loom before me every moment, offering their endless advice and help. I could not let them see what I was. Who had ever heard of a mother with such an unnatural void in her heart for her own child? (p.224)

The significance of Phaedra's incapability of embracing motherhood is further shown through her indifference to her child which reaches the extent that she did not want to participate in naming him

When Theseus came to lay his eyes upon his son, I watched him with curiosity. He seemed pleased enough, if not particularly interested. I envied him his untroubled indifference. (...) 'What is his name?' Theseus asked. I shrugged. I did not trust myself to speak. The shattering fatigue that split me apart might let anything slip out if I opened my mouth. (p.224)

It's additionally essential to take into account Phaedra internalised her guilt as a result of her inability to accept her position. Subconsciously, the character realised that her son's presence disrupted her normalcy as a woman. This is crucial because Phaedra's personality changed from being somewhat brave, assertive, and masculine to a meek young woman who protected herself by acting the part of a queen:

But the Minotaur had been an aberration, I told myself. I forced myself to look at my son's little face and I tried to feel, deep in my heart, the connection that should exist between mother and child. He had been born of me, after all. Why did I look at him and see a stranger? He was no product of an unspeakable deed. He was not a hideous half-being; my baby was human at least. Why then did it feel so difficult to love him? I did not know. (p.133)

Furthermore, Phaedra's character underwent a drastic transformation and regression brought on by the cultural factors in her environment, becoming increasingly helpless and infantile. This is demonstrated by the way the author portrays her character's urgency to escape Athens in her final few points of view. Phaedra's character exhibits an intriguing, though immature, change when Ariadne pays her a visit as she starts to yearn for Hippolytus' affection. Not to be overlooked is the fact that her stepson Hippolytus was a devout follower of Artemis and possessed numerous qualities that do not belong in the "masculine" category:

"I saw how Hippolytus guided this vast and powerful creature with the gentlest of touches – he did not crack a whip or yell into its ear as I had seen Theseus do so many times to his steeds, reducing them to cowering shadows of themselves" (P.248).

Therefore, Phaedra sees him as her last hope in escaping her position. Phaedra iludes herself into thinking that she wants a relationship with him, but as the action progresses and he turns her down, it becomes clear that her desperation was not motivated solely by love for Hippolytus—rather, he was her last-ditch attempt to escape. Phaedra thus turned to hanging herself as a last resort when Hippolytus rejected her.

Saint's approach to Phaedra's tragic ending is rather significant. While the character embodied many characteristics out of her gender binary, she was deemed to submit to her fate as the social structure constantly shut down her attempts to be herself. Initially, Phaedra's development showcased her as an aware woman that would never submit to her fate. However, the character's limitations led her to be contained in a box with no access to any other opportunities. Consequently, Saint demonstrates how the character's development regresses by the end of the retelling of her life due to the defence mechanism she used to delude herself into thinking that she would be able to achieve what she wanted despite her circumstances.

CONCLUSION

Gender studies is a multidisciplinary field that analyses the complex connections between gender and other identifying characteristics such as race, ethnicity, sexual orientation, class, and nationality. It assesses the ways in which gender affects people's experiences, social structures, and cultural manifestations. Any connection between biology and gender is rejected by gender theory as physiological fundamentalism. One of the most well-known voices in gender theory, Judith Butler, asserts that gender—the way a person expresses their gender identity—and the biological fact of sex are social creations. There are roles that are "performed" by men and women. Consequently, gender can be recreated, just like the body. Additionally, the critical analysis of the ways in which gender affects cultural norms, societal systems, and personal identities demonstrates the importance of gender studies; this field of study goes beyond just challenging preconceived views about gender and sex in order to continuously outline and work towards transforming the common understanding of these concepts. In order to question and reshape the cultural narratives that have long shaped gender norms, gender studies therefore became crucial.

The foundation of gender theory was explored in this thesis by delving back promptly to examine its origins, core concepts, connections to and overlaps with Feminism, Marxism, patriarchy, and the social structures of numerous nations, cultures, and racial groups. Gender is shown to be an imposed social construction throughout the research, acting as a tool to establish a hierarchical pyramid that assigns women to specific positions and disadvantages them within the power system. This study comprehensively illustrates the process of othering women as the second sex and a sub gender, drawing on Beauvoir's thesis in *The Second Sex*, Rubin Gayle's notion of the gender/sex system, Audre Lorde's line of argument regarding the limitation of women's power and voice, and Butler's assertion that gender in its very essence a notion performativity.

Furthermore, through Madeline Miller's novel *Circe*, it is navigated through a theoretical lens how the author emphasises the feminine body throughout the novel as the main motif. This thesis asserted the vitality of Miller's approach to her character's body as the entire novel offers a comprehensive view of the physical limitations and the transformation that come with being a "nymph" and subsequently a "witch.". It is

demonstrated in the first section of the analysis that Miller intended to highlight the physical circumstances of her character as one of the main notions that would help to define and support her development within the patriarchal gender structure of her immediate environment. In Miller's retelling, women are objectified as the inferior gender in order to highlight the hierarchical structure that limits their power and to emphasise how their opportunities and responsibilities are shaped by society. This is amply illustrated via the ways in which Circe was forced to deal with the male characters' never-ending battle of "ownership." The study demonstrates how Circe was treated like a property and how, rather than fulfilling any of her desires, she was taught to exploit her body to get attention from men. Beauvoir's theory of the second sex as a subgenre of the "general" gender—in this case, the male gender—is applied to analyse these cases.

Moreover, in line with Lorde's focus on the significance of poetics and Gayle's theory of the social gender system, this work examines how Miller uses Circe's voice as a weapon on several occasions as distinct themes to elicit changes in her character. Throughout the analysis of this study, these concepts are examined. Firstly, being through the way she was silenced, following that, the interconnections of her Pharmaka and voice; considering her ownership of her body comes from her ability to speak and cast her spells, Miller's utilisation of Circe's voice easily comes in line with Lorde's thesis. Furthermore, the author's weaponization of Circe's isolation can be perceived through a theoretical lens in accordance with Butler's idea of performativity. This is demonstrated in the way the island is a newly set stage that is away from the practical system that is heavily based on the gender binary. When Circe is isolated in Aiaia, it is navigated that the character's identity undergoes an entire transformation that sets her away from the standard idea of her gender. Nonetheless, Miller's approach to her character showcases the process of Circe's liberation as well the extent of the patriarchal power and elements that the character faces for not conforming to her gender role. This is examined thoroughly following Cahil's notion of women as pre victims as well Beauvoir's views on women's subjectification to certain roles that place them at a disadvantage. This occurs when Circe deals with the sailor visitors; the character finds herself constantly confined back to the patriarchal system she had escaped, thus, any interaction with the outside world heavily impacted the extent of power she could yield, such a process is demonstrated in a board manner through the rape sequence and its aftermath. Miller utilises Circe's constant transformation and hinders as a circular theme

throughout the novel; in order to present the character as a naked model as a whole, the author successfully navigates the connections of Circe's transformation of identity to her body.

Miller employs a metaphorical voice to convey to readers the importance of having the courage to stand up for oneself and share one's own experience. She does this by delving into a complex cast of female characters that are both terrifying and strong in their own unique ways. This is crucial since addressing the already-imposed gender binary comes at the expense of the character act of breaking gender in and of itself. Throughout the examination, Butler's theory of gender performativity is broadened to encompass the bodily components of the novel as well as the settings; Miller weaponizes Circe's body as both a challenge and a vital part of the character's journey to complete her transformation. In this context, the study examined Miller's careful approach to the heroine's bodily attributes and her eventual embracement of her natural instincts such as her empathy and motherhood. Within the framework of revisionist mythmaking, the author showcases the character's final act of breaking gender and finding herself by illuminating the character's ability to embrace her 'vulnerabilities', in this case her mortality. Although Circe stays inside the patriarchal discourse throughout the novel, having access to magic allowed her character to step out of the performative stage she was subjected to and allowed her to both accept and abandon parts of herself to become anew. Thus, Circe's ultimate metamorphosis can be considered the best opportunity for her to continuously be herself and change as an individual. It is clear that her ultimate abandonment of immortality symbolises her whole demise and rebirth of herself. In this framework, Miller highlights how transformation is a continuous process that never ends in this way.

Similarly to Madeline Miller's approach to Circe, Jennifer Saint's retelling of Ariadne adapts a homogeneous thesis throughout the novel. In the third chapter of this thesis, Saint's implementation of the heroine's perspective is thoroughly navigated in accordance with both Gayle Rubin's concept of gender system and Audre Lorde's assertion in regards the female experience as the lesser gender. Jennifer Saint's employment of the heroine's point of view to create a unique representation of gender and modern feminist theories is carefully examined in the analysis. As the author uses these representations to her advantage while embodying them. Saint provides a new reading of the myth, which she embodies without transforming. Like Miller's Circe, in

order to study the development and tragedy of her character in great detail. Her writing skilfully traces the development of her sister Phaedra while also scrutinising and questioning Ariadne's choices and growth. By fusing the two viewpoints, the author illuminates the ways in which women fight against the dominance of men, their own rage, the challenges of motherhood and womanhood, and the political struggle inside a social structure that doesn't give much weight to a woman's existence. Saint's approach in this case differs from Miller's as she thoroughly examines each of these aspects in her debut work, using the lives of several women as a model. Through that, the author shows how the women's status within the social and gendered framework of their immediate surroundings doomed them all to the same end in each case. Nonetheless, it has also been navigated how by growing up hearing stories of gods and legendary epics, Ariadne's life is chronicled throughout the novel as she embraces her dancing and her childhood dream of marrying a hero. Ironically, she ultimately rebels against the gods and everyone around her to make sure she plays the part. This development can be seen going hand in hand with Miller's approach to Circe's earlier life. Similarly to Ariadne, both characters witness a shift in their identity whilst trying to conform to their gender role. Nevertheless, like many other female mythological figures, Ariadne was a victim left behind to uphold Theseus's heroic heritage. Saint utilises this mythology to confront and address the ways in which these old and classical myths depict women as a cost that those men must bear as a result of their lust, fury, and greed.

Furthermore, in line with Beauvoir's thesis and Butler's idea of breaking gender, Saint also explores the life of Phaedra, Ariadne's sister and the younger princess, emphasising her challenges and the constant marginalisation she experiences as a result of her gender as well as her attempts to transcend these limitations. Through the analysis, it is noted that in Crete, Ariadne and Phaedra both had to deal with Theseus' betrayal to break the imposed perfected stage they lived in, in this case being Crete. This betrayal both allows the characters to achieve a shift in their roles and gain a conscious awareness of their position in the systematic social power. In this way, Saint allows us to use a theoretical lens to both examine Ariadne's isolation and its impact on her identity transformation and the regression of Phaedra's development due to the confinements of her immediate environment and social system. In this aspect, both characters' development can be compared to Circe's growth. In Miller's work, the author adapts the complete isolation of Circe to showcase her development in a boundless environment,

similarly to Ariadne, the character sees an immense growth and illustrates an ongoing process of breaking her gender. On the other hand, just like Phaedra, Circe's development deals with challenging regression when dealing with the outside elements that conform to the gender system, for instance, her experience with rape and assault by the visitors of the island confines Circe's identity in a constant loop that was controlled by her rage. All three heroines in this case are seen to have an interconnection in both their environment and identity growth and struggles.

In accordance with Gayle's notion of the gender system, Ariadne's isolation is navigated in terms of the new environment and its impact on the character's gender and development. Throughout the heroine's perspective it is noted that the character is able to both embrace her femininity and find strength in herself, allowing her to completely achieve independence outside of the patriarchal system. This is shown in multiple instances such as in the manner she adapts to the island she was casted to, her ability to achieve an equal standing with Dionysus as well her last final act to liberate herself from being an object and a victim of the male domain and power. Considering the female characters of Greek mythology were never given a voice, the novel provides them one through a mesmerising yet incredibly powerful epic that seamlessly integrates into the original narrative. Like Miller, Saint aims to show that these female figures have heroic qualities and duties that are just as valuable as those of the male heroes by entirely altering many aspects of them. The characters' development and attempts to stray from their gender norms in pursuit of their true selves are also highlighted in the retelling, following Butler's dissertation of the act of breaking gender. This is achieved through the way the author illustrates how her character was raised in a culture that saw her as a woman constrained by her gender and as a possible victim of men's acts. Thus, when navigating her realisation of both her predicament and her mother's tragedy, it is perceived a change took place in her subconscious. Her first rebellion and effort to flee with Theseus for example, demonstrate the constraints she was exposed to in the society systems since she would always be an object first and foremost, intended to gratify male characters. Moreover, this study explores the heroine's final breaking of identity as the last scene develops, highlighting the character's wilfulness. Even though it is tragic unlike Circe, the play's ending translates into an empowering one: Ariadne's attempt to stop the madness and her subsequent victimisation amid the clashing show a brave,

empowering act that symbolises her transformation into a struggling human trapped in a societal mould that made her a victim just like all those ancient Greek women.

On the other hand, this study also examined Saint's perspective on Phaedra's tragic conclusion. Withstanding how the character possessed many traits that defied the gender binary, the social structure continuously prevented her from becoming who she truly wanted to be, so she was forced to accept her fate. Similarly to Circe's constant challenge with the outside elements that invaded her island and thus subjected her character to a regression, Phaedra's growth at first showed her as a conscious individual who would never accept her circumstances. But the character's constraints kept her confined to a space where she had no access to other possibilities. As a result, Saint shows how the character's growth regresses towards the end of the retelling that was caused by her need for survival. Consequently, It is considered that the story does not explicitly offer a happy ending or a solution for women. However, it sensitively emphasises the range of sufferings and does not diminish the experience a woman goes through to liberate herself from her limits by placing "male" attributes on the characters. In this context, it is understood through this study of the novel that pursuing equality does not mean being conceited, arrogant, or needing to be emotionally detached. Instead, the author focuses on showing how the idea of sub gendering women is intended to dehumanise and marginalise women, which goes in line with Beauvoir's idea of the second sex.

Consequently, both Madeline Miller and Jennifer Saint's retellings did not shy away from explicitly feminist themes. Both novels navigated the patriarchal discourse and the societal gendered ideology that reflect the gender distinction and binary that is imposed on women. In such framework, both authors make no effort to obscure the motivation for their retellings: both write about women, for women, perfectly reflecting the oppressive systems that their characters attempt to break constantly. Moreover, they de-villainise their characters and present them as their own heroines, instead of weaponizing them for glorified heroes' legacies. By doing so, they successfully offer their characters not only a voice, but an identity of their own, severing their connotations with those mythological male heroes and the social system they were subjected to.

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